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Bioguided fractionation of *Gambierdiscus* extracts

Gambierdiscus excentricus (Fraga et al., 2011)

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“But in a way you can say that after leaving the sea, after all those millions of years of living inside of the sea, we took the ocean with us. [...] Our blood and our sweating, they are both salty, almost exactly like the water from the sea is salty. We carry oceans inside of us, in our blood and our sweat. And we are crying the oceans, in our tears.”

Gregory David Roberts, *Shantaram*

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CHAPTER ONE

INTRODUCTION

1.1. Ciguatera Fish Poisoning

1.1.1. Background

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) is a form of ichthyosarcotoxism, i.e. a poisoning caused by the ingestion of fish whose flesh contains a toxic substance. CFP is one of the most common non-bacterial food-borne intoxication caused by consuming fish contaminated by ciguatoxins (CTXs) (Bagnis et al., 1980; Friedman et al., 2008).

Epidemiological characterization of CFP has been limited by the lack of laboratory tests able to confirm the presence of CTXs. In the absence of a human biomarker CFP, the anamnesis is based on the clinical scenario and the patient's recent fish-eating history. Ciguatera syndrome manifests itself as gastrointestinal, neurological, and, in severe cases, cardiovascular symptoms. The distinctive clinical sign of CFP is allodynia, i.e. the inversion of the perception of temperature, wherein a cold spot induces a burning sensation. The duration, severity and number of symptoms depend on the amount of CTXs consumed, the type of fish ingested (herbivorous, carnivorous) and the location from which the fish was caught. Poisoning can also cause long-term effects, e.g. asthenia and depression, which can last for months or even years.

This poisoning affects approximately between 50,000 and 500,000 consumers annually worldwide. The true incidence of CFP is difficult to ascertain, due to under-reporting and misdiagnosis (Lewis, 2001). This high incidence is due to the lack of health management, the high potency of the causative toxins (poisoning occurs at very low concentrations) and

the fact that carnivorous fishes sometimes migrate over long distances, hampering the determination of the origin of the intoxication.

In France, CFP has long been known in the overseas islands (e.g. French Polynesia, Martinique, La Réunion). In the last decade, the increased incidence of CFP in the Pacific Ocean and the Caribbean Sea, as well as the presence of *Gambierdiscus* in the Mediterranean Sea and North-Eastern Atlantic Ocean, require additional efforts in terms of detection and prevention.

The study of CFP has been declared as a priority in May 2012 at the Intergovernmental Oceanographic Commission of UNESCO (IOC-UNESCO), Intergovernmental Panel on Harmful Algal Blooms (HAB). Since 2013, the laboratory "Phycotoxins" (IFREMER, Nantes) has intensified its research on ciguatera, by i) implementing the culture of microalgae responsible for poisoning at the laboratory and ii) introducing methods of detection and quantification of the toxins. It is in this context that my internship took place.

1.1.2. Geographical distribution of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning

Ciguatera Fish Poisoning has long been reported from tropical and subtropical areas of the Pacific Ocean, the Caribbean Sea and the Indian Ocean (Lewis, 2001).

Poisoning cases have also been reported in more temperate areas (e.g. the United States, Canada and Europe) and have been related to tourism or to the importation of fish from endemic areas (Geller et al., 1991).

In the last decade the geographical distribution of CFP is expanding in new areas previously not considered as endemic (Figure 1). In the Eastern Atlantic, particularly in the Canary Islands, cases of CFP have occurred (at least 14 outbreaks since 2005) (Boada et al., 2010) and new species of the causative microalgae *Gambierdiscus* have been described (Fraga et al., 2011; Fraga and Rodriguez, 2014). In the Mediterranean Sea, the presence of *Gambierdiscus* has been observed since 2003 but poisoning outbreaks have not been recorded yet (Aligizaki, 2008). The detection of the tropical genus *Gambierdiscus* in the North-Eastern Atlantic Ocean and in the Mediterranean Sea, along with the confirmation

of CFP cases in the Canary Islands and suspected cases in Madeira and Cameroun, are at the origin of my thesis project.

Figure 1. World distribution of ciguatera (www.ciguatera-online.com/index.php/fr/nos-services/geographie-des-intoxications (2014)).

The spatio-temporal correlation between a CFP outbreak at a given time in a certain location and the presence of *Gambierdiscus* in seawater is difficult to highlight. In the first place, all species and strains of *Gambierdiscus* are not equally toxic, therefore a *Gambierdiscus* bloom does not necessarily translate in a CFP episode. In the second place, fish are moving vectors, usually covering long-distance migrations: this fact hampers an accurate spatial correlation. Finally, the bioaccumulation of toxins in fish flesh along the marine food chain is a long-term process (Legrand et al., 1992). These factors lead to the conclusion that, at the onset of an episode of ciguatera, significant concentrations of the causative toxic microalgae in seawater will not necessarily be found.

The abundance and distribution of *Gambierdiscus* spp., as long as their capability in producing CTXs, is routinely monitored in endemic areas of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning. The occurrence of toxic (CTX-producing) *Gambierdiscus* spp. blooms may be used as a bio-indicator of local ciguatera risk in a specific area (Bentur and Spanier, 2007). The appearance of CTX-containing herbivorous fish may occur some months after a toxic

Gambierdiscus bloom. Determination of CTXs in phytoplankton samples containing *Gambierdiscus* spp. may also have importance for geographical ciguatera risk assessment (Parsons et al., 2012). Determination of CTX production by *Gambierdiscus* spp. cultures, in parallel with taxonomic studies of the genus *Gambierdiscus*, is crucial for associating toxin production with a particular *Gambierdiscus* species (Caillaud et al., 2010a). These studies are important to evaluate the intrinsic factors, such as the genetic pattern of a given strain, and the extrinsic factors, such as the environmental conditions favorable to toxin production (Bourdy et al., 1992).

1.1.3. Poisoning routes

Ciguatera poisoning generally occurs when large reef fish contaminated by ciguatoxins are consumed. Ciguatoxins (CTXs) are not produced by the fish themselves; the primary producers of CTXs are benthic dinoflagellates of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*. CTXs are biomagnified up through the marine food web: herbivorous fish take up the toxins by ingesting toxic clones of the microalgae that colonized new or denuded surfaces of dead corals. Carnivorous fish, in turn, become toxic feeding on contaminated herbivorous fish (Parsons et al., 2012). Helfrich and Banner (1963) demonstrated that the toxins could be transferred from ciguateric fish flesh into non-toxic fish, thereby providing evidence for trophic transfer in the food web. (Halstead, 1978) reported that 400 species of herbivorous, omnivorous and carnivorous fish have caused ciguatera, although this number may mainly be based on local estimates (Bagnis et al., 1990). Nevertheless, it is likely that CTXs move throughout the piscivorous food web resulting in numerous species accumulating ciguatoxins. Some examples of CFP vectors are shown in figure 2.

Vector fish of ciguatera toxins

Figure 2. Examples of fish implicated in Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (photo credit by: Yasuwo Fukuyo, UNESCO).

Greater illness severity is associated with the consumption of larger portions of fish flesh or the ingestion of fish viscera (Lewis and King, 1996). Thus, people are advised to avoid eating the viscera of reef fish. It is also advisable to avoid consuming large predatory reef fish from areas known to be associated with CFP. With regard to fish size, avoidance of fish in excess of 3 kilograms (approximately 6.6 pounds), or even more conservatively, avoidance of fish in excess of 1.35 kilograms (approximately 3 pounds) has been recommended. It has also been proposed that eating small portions (i.e. < 50 grams or < 0.11 pounds) of different fish is safer than eating larger portions of any individual fish that might be associated with CFP (Lewis and King, 1996). Nevertheless, a study conducted by Gaboriau et al. (2014) concluded that "size does not always matter", alerting that small herbivorous fish could be as toxic as large predatory ones. The authors provided evidence

when analyzing 859 fishes from Marquesas, Tuamotu and Australes archipelagos, using RBA (Receptor Binding Assay) method.

Table 1. List of commonly ciguatoxic fish to avoid, although any large coral reef fish has the potential to be ciguatoxic. Of note, recent reports suggest that CFP may be associated not only with coral reefs, but also with oil rigs and other artificial reefs (inspired from Table 4 (Friedman et al., 2008)).

Fish avoidance recommendations
<i>Some common Ciguatoxic Fish</i>
Moray eel
Barracuda
Grouper
Kingfish
Jacks
Snapper
Surgeonfish
Parrot fish
Wrasses
Hogfish
Narrow barred Spanish mackerel
Coral trout
Flowery cod
Red emperor
<i>The following are also associated with CFP</i>
Eating fish viscera or roe
Large, predatory reef fish*
Reef fish from areas known to be associated with CFP occurrence
Note that eating small portions (i.e. <50 grams or <0.11 pounds) of different fish may be safer than eating larger portions (i.e. >200 grams) of any one potentially ciguatoxic fish.
*Lange <i>et al.</i>, 1987 cites a recommendation to not eat fish larger than 1.35-2.25 kg (3-5pounds), whereas Ting and Brown (2001) recommend not eating fish larger than 3 kg (6.6 pounds).

In recent years, potential CFP vectors, other than reef fish, have been highlighted. This is the case of giant clams (Roué et al., 2013) , gastropods (Lonati et.al, 2015) and starfish (Silva et al., 2015).

An atypical ciguatera-like syndrome called Ciguatera Shellfish Poisoning (CSP) has been described in Vanuatu, New Caledonia and French Polynesia after the consumption of giant clams (Roué et al., 2013). The LC-MS/MS confirmation of the presence of CTXs in giant clams (*Tridacna maxima*) after exposure to *Gambierdiscus* spp. cells provided evidence for this alternative route of exposure (Roué et al., 2016). These atypical cases were associated to additional symptoms such as the burning of the mouth and the throat, sometimes followed by severe paralysis, probably due to the involvement of other families of toxins. Some cyanobacteria of the genus *Trichodesmium* are also suspected to be involved (Roué et al., 2016), (Kerbrat et al., 2010). Gastropods (e.g. *Tectus niloticus*) have been found to be new potential CTX vectors as well (Lonati et al., 2015).

A recent study conducted by Silva et al. (Silva et al., 2015) showed that echinoderms might also be potential CTX vectors. UPLC-IT-TOF-MS and UPLC-MS/MS techniques are used to show the presence of CTXs in two species of starfish (*Ophidaster ophidianus* and *Marthasterias glacialis*) collected in Madeira and Azores. *O. ophidianus* had both higher probability of showing positive results and significantly higher amount of toxin per body mass, because of its detritivorous nature, that is in contrast with the predatory one from *M. glacialis*. Therefore, starfish seems to represent an alternative CFP vector. The authors proposed to use starfish for ciguatera monitoring to better evaluate human health risk, but still little is known about the eventual CTX uptake between echinoderms and predatory fish (Silva et al., 2015).

1.1.4. Symptomatology

Ciguatera syndrome manifests itself as gastrointestinal, neurological, and, in severe cases, cardiovascular symptoms (Friedman et al., 2008).

General signs are characterized by asthenia, associated with several other signs such as nervousness, headache, toothache, lipothymic trend, photophobia, blurred vision, hypersalivation, ejaculation pain, lowering of the rectal temperature.

Cutaneous signs mainly consist in a continuous itching.

Gastro-intestinal signs are characterized by vomit, nausea, abdominal cramps, and diarrhea.

Neurological signs may vary among patients and include the following: paresthesia (numbness and tingling) in the extremities (feet and hands) and oral region, generalized pruritus (itching), myalgia (muscle pain), arthralgia (joint pain), and tiredness. A distinctive symptom, reported by many patients, is allodynia, which is an alteration or “reversal” of hot/cold temperature perception, in which cold surfaces are perceived as hot by the patient. Temperature-related diseases have been reported not only in CFP but also in Neurotoxic Shellfish Poisoning (NSP, caused by human consumption of shellfish contaminated by brevetoxins) (Friedman et al., 2008). As a consequence, if there is a history of eating shellfish, the diagnosis of NSP has to be considered.

Neuropsychiatric symptoms in CFP may include anxiety, depression and subjectively reported memory loss (Arena et al., 2004). These symptoms can last months, even years. More marked mental status changes such as hallucinations, giddiness (Quod and Turquet, 1996), incoordination or ataxia (Quod and Turquet, 1996) and coma have been reported.

Cardiovascular and respiratory signs are the most dangerous ones, and include the following: hypotension, bradycardia, bradyarrhythmia or extrasystoles that could lead to collapse. The fatigability of muscles involved in respiratory movements is responsible for dyspnea. These signs require the intervention of qualified personnel.

CFP is rarely fatal. However, death may occur in severe cases due to severe dehydration, cardiovascular shock, during the initial illness period, or respiratory failure resulting from paralysis of the respiratory musculature, especially in areas where artificial respiratory support and emergency medical care are unavailable (Friedman et al., 2008). The mortality rate due to ciguatera intoxication is low. According to Ruff and Lewis (1994) it

would represent only 0.1% of the reported cases. However, in the case of a massive intoxication, the mortality rate may reach even 20% (Habermehl et al., 1994).

If the symptoms persist for years, chronic ciguatera intoxication is considered, and it evolves in chronic fatigue syndrome (Pearn, 1997). Wang et al. (2016) provided evidence that chronic ciguatoxin poisoning causes emotional and cognitive dysfunctions in rats.

The intoxication generally manifests itself in three stages that can have different nature and amplitude (Boydron-Le Garrec, 2004):

a) Lag Phase

The lag phase is the time elapsed between the ingestion of ciguateric fish and the appearance of the first symptoms. It can vary from few minutes to 48 hours (in 90% of the cases the symptoms appear in less than 12 hours). The duration of the lag phase depends on: (a) the dose of ingested toxins; (b) the exposure and (c) the individual susceptibility.

b) Prodromal Period

The prodromal period is characterized by gastrointestinal diseases, which can be isolated or associated with neurological symptoms. Gastrointestinal symptoms (*e.g.* vomiting, diarrhea, abdominal pain, nausea) usually develop within 6-24 hours of eating a reportedly good-tasting reef fish and resolve spontaneously, or in response to symptomatic treatments, within 1-4 days.

c) Status Phase

The status phase can last from some days to several weeks, sometimes even months. General and neurological signs appear at the beginning, and they could be associated with persistent cutaneous and gastrointestinal diseases. Cardio-vascular and respiratory signs are rare, but, if they appear, could be fatal.

Recurrence of ciguatera symptoms have been reported in individuals that previously suffered from CFP, even years after the first exposure. This phenomenon of **sensitization** generally occurs after eating a potentially ciguateric fish that do not produce symptoms on other individuals, but it can also occur when consuming certain other food in combination with alcohol (Friedman et al., 2008). Friedman et al. (2008) suggested that during the first

exposure CTXs may be stored in adipose tissue as a result of their lipophilicity. A change in lipid metabolism could cause the re-entering of CTXs in the blood stream and, consequently, the re-emergence of CFP symptoms.

Another possible explanation for sensitization could be related with immunological-mediated reaction to CTXs, after the first exposure (Friedman et al., 2008).

1.1.5. Treatments

Unfortunately, a specific antidote for ciguatera intoxication does not exist yet. As a consequence, only symptomatic and support treatments are currently prescribed.

For example, in New Caledonia's traditional medicine, infusions of *Argusia argentea* leaves are used to treat ciguatera intoxication. Several studies demonstrate that this popular treatment reduces the effects of ciguatoxins on mice (Amade and Laurent, 1992) and on frog's myelinated axons (Benoit et al., 2000).

Antiemetic and/or anti-diarrhea drugs are generally prescribed for the gastro-intestinal symptoms, antihistamine drugs are used for treating itching and atropine is used for cardiovascular disease (e.g. bradycardia). In case of hypotension, a correction can be done using crystalloids or hydroxyethyl starch (Boydron-Le Garrec, 2004).

In case of hydro-electrolytic diseases, hospitalization has to be considered, especially if the patient is a high-risk individual (e.g. children, aged people).

Vitamin B6 deficiency and ciguatera cause similar symptoms, so large doses of vitamin B1, B6 and B12 are used to treat ciguatera as well. Treatment with Calcium gluconate (10%) and corticoids is done by intravenous (*iv*) route. D-mannitol (20% solution, *iv*) is used in case of severe neurological symptoms as emergency treatment (Ruff and Lewis, 1994).

1.1.6. Socio-economic consequences of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning

Fish are the main source of protein, and most island communities consume well over 100 g of fish per person per day (Stafford and Bell, 2009). Yet an exclusive reliance on fish can be disastrous for an island population when those resources contain high concentrations of ciguatoxins and become inedible (Rongo et al., 2009) . Beyond the human health issues,

ciguatera poisoning has caused socio-economic problems in both developing and developed countries. These issues include: increased health-related cost, loss of labour productivity, loss of a food source, loss of reef-fish sales in both local and international markets, loss of tourism, and depopulation through migration (Rongo et al., 2012).

Small-island nations experiencing extensive ciguatera poisoning may undergo to dietary shifts away from reef fish (Lewis and Endean, 1983). The shift away from a fresh fish diet appears to have also contributed to the increased prevalence of non-communicable diseases among Pacific island populations because alternative protein sources (*e.g.* canned foods) typically have high fat and salt contents (Rongo and van Woesik, 2012). However, the nature of the alternative protein source depends on the economic status of the islands involved.

Rarotonga Island represents an example of dietary shift from fresh fish to different food sources, as shown in figure 3. The study conducted by Rongo and van Woesik (2012) was based on the amount of protein consumed in the week before the 2011 survey. Overall, 89% of Rarotongan households indicated that chicken was a major part (37%) of their protein intake. Seventy-four percent of households consumed fresh fish, which contributed to 33% of the total protein intake; other meats and canned goods (*i.e.* canned fish and corned beef) were also important sources of protein.

Figure 3. Per-capita percent contribution of each food item to total protein intake of 179 Rarotongan households surveyed in 2011 (Rongo and van Woesik, 2012).

1.2. The dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus*

1.2.1. Background

Planktonic harmful algal blooms have a long history of study. The study of harmful benthic microalgae, conversely, did not commence until the mid-1970s, when Yasumoto et al. (1977) reported the discovery of a benthic dinoflagellate responsible for ciguatera, the most common form of phycotoxin-borne seafood illness across the globe (Yasumoto et al., 1977). Subsequent studies described many benthic dinoflagellates, including *Gambierdiscus toxicus* Adachi and Fukuyo, the dinoflagellate reported by Yasumoto et al. (1977) and later described by (Adachi and Fukuyo, 1979), and *Ostreopsis ovata* Fukuyo described by (Fukuyo, 1981), a species later found to be toxic as well (Nakajima et al., 1981). More recent studies focused on the ecology and toxicology of these and other benthic dinoflagellates (*e.g.* *Prorocentrum* and *Coolia*), with a particular concern in the study of *Gambierdiscus* due to its role in ciguatera.

1.2.2. Taxonomy

The dinoflagellate *Gambierdiscus* was originally described by Yasumoto's group using live and preserved materials collected from the Gambier Islands (French Polynesia) (Adachi and Fukuyo, 1979). This genus had been considered monospecific for fifteen years with *Gambierdiscus toxicus* Adachi & Fukuyo (Adachi and Fukuyo, 1979) as the only described species. Later on, the diversity of the genus was found to be much higher than expected and new species have recently been added to the genus (Chinain et al., 1999) (Litaker et al., 2009) based on both morphology and genetics, which helped to find semicryptic species (Litaker et al., 2009).

Richlen et al. (2008) summarized the physiological variability within *G. toxicus*, highlighted in earlier studies, including differences in growth rates, toxin production, electrophoretic profiles of isozymes, and genetic sequences (Richlen et al., 2008). Despite these earlier observations on morphological and physiological variability within *G. toxicus*, it was still considered as one single species. Thus, several studies, regarding toxicity, biology, physiology, and ecology cannot be attributed with confidence to a specific *Gambierdiscus* species (Fraga et al., 2011).

Another dinoflagellate genus named *Fukuyoa* has recently been distinguished from *Gambierdiscus* by (Gómez et al., 2015). The authors proposed a name for a new species isolated from Brazil, *F. paulensis*, and they transferred two globular species of *Gambierdiscus* into the *Fukuyoa* genus (*F. yasumotoi* and *F. ruetzleri*).

According to Gomez et al. (2015) the distinction of these two genera is justified by: (i) differences in cell shape (lenticular for *Gambierdiscus*, globular for *Fukuyoa*) and plate arrangement (morphology and pattern), and (ii) the considerable evolutionary distance of their respective SSU and LSU rDNA sequences, which form two well-separated clades (Gómez et al., 2015) (figure 4).

Figure 4. LSU rDNA-based phylogeny of *Fukuyoa paulensis* gen. et sp. nov. and *Goniiodoma polyedricum* with some gonyaulacoid dinoflagellates. *Oxyrrhis marina* was used as outgroup (Gómez et al., 2015).

In table 2 all the species and phylotypes described within *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* genera are listed.

Table 2. *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* species/phylotypes with references.

Genus	Species / Phylotype	Reference
<i>Gambierdiscus</i>	<i>G. australes</i>	(Chinain et al., 1999)
	<i>G. belizeanus</i>	(Faust, 1995)
	<i>G. caribaeus</i>	(Litaker et al., 2009)
	<i>G. carolinianus</i>	(Litaker et al., 2009)
	<i>G. carpenteri</i>	(Litaker et al., 2009)
	<i>G. excentricus</i>	(Fraga et al., 2011)
	<i>G. pacificus</i>	(Chinain et al., 1999)
	<i>G. polynesiensis</i>	(Chinain et al., 1999)
	<i>G. scabrosus**</i>	(Nishimura et al., 2014)
	<i>G. silvae</i>	(Fraga and Rodriguez, 2014)
	<i>G. sp. ribotype II</i>	*
	<i>G. sp. type 2</i>	(Kuno et al., 2010)
	<i>G. sp. type 3</i>	*
	<i>G. sp. type 4</i>	(Xu et al., 2014)
	<i>G. sp. type 5</i>	(Xu et al., 2014)
	<i>G. sp. type 6</i>	*
<i>G. toxicus</i>	(Adachi and Fukuyo, 1979)	
<i>Fukuyoa</i>	<i>F. paulensis</i>	(Gómez et al., 2015)
	<i>F. ruetzleri****</i>	(Gómez et al., 2015)
	<i>F. yasumotoi***</i>	(Gómez et al., 2015)

* species not described, only cited by Xu et al. (2014)

** formerly called *G. sp. type 1* (Xu et al., 2014)

*** formerly described as *G. yasumotoi* (Holmes, 1998).

**** formerly described as *G. ruetzleri* (Litaker et al., 2009).

1.2.3. Geographical distribution of the genus *Gambierdiscus*

A study conducted by Nishimura et al. (2013) showed that species of *Gambierdiscus* were not distributed homogeneously over the globe.

G. belizeanus, *G. carolinianus*, *F. ruetzleri* were found exclusively in the Atlantic Ocean, whereas *G. australes*, *G. pacificus*, *G. polynesiensis*, *G. toxicus*, and *F. yasumotoi* were found only in the Pacific Ocean. *G. caribaeus* and *G. carpenteri* were found in both Atlantic

and Pacific Oceans. Species endemic to each region tend to be widely dispersed. The factors underlying the cosmopolitan distribution of *G. caribaeus* and *G. carpenteri* have yet to be determined, but may be related to an unusually broad temperature tolerance compared to other *Gambierdiscus* species (Tester et al., 2010). *G. caribaeus* growth range is from 22 up to 33 °C. It was also the most commonly isolated species in both the Pacific and Atlantic Oceans (Litaker et al., 2010).

Tindall and Morton (1998) reported boundaries of approximately 32°N and 35°S for *Gambierdiscus*, but since those boundaries have shifted. Hallegraeff (2010) recently reported *G. toxicus* at 37°S. Later on, a possible new species of *Gambierdiscus* was found at 35°N in the Mediterranean Sea (Parsons et al., 2012). Xu et al. (2016) concluded that the greatest latitude of distribution are approximately 38.5°N and 47.1°S.

1.2.4. Life cycle of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

Gambierdiscus spp. have a cell cycle longer than 24h diurnal cycle and they have a division rate of 0.15 day⁻¹ (it means that only 15% of cells are progressing to mitosis in one photoperiod). The mechanism by which the circadian clock controls the cell cycle is still unclear, because the molecular regulators affecting the dinoflagellate cycle are not discovered yet (VanDolah and Ramsdell, 1996). Van Dolah et al. (1996) demonstrated the presence of CDC2 kinase (a cell cycle regulatory protein) in *G. toxicus*, and it is constitutively expressed through the life cycle. The maximal expression of CDC2 occurs when mitotic cells are present, like in the other eukaryotes (VanDolah and Ramsdell, 1996).

Figure 5. Life cycle of *G. toxicus* (Hokama et al., 1996b).

Figure 5 shows the life cycle of *G. toxicus* cultivated in laboratory (Hokama et al., 1996a). At time 0 it is possible to observe *Gambierdiscus* cells in a *motile free phase* (A). After 2-3 weeks, they enter a *precyst phase* in which cells become immobile and dark. It is also possible to observe dense intracellular pigment and an initial secretion of mucoid sheath (B). In the *cyst phase*, cells have a thick mucoid sheath and dark pigments (C). A secondary cyst, with thinner cell wall (D) is able to do mitosis, in an extension from thick mucoid wall (E). It is possible to observe about 20 divisions per cyst, and then cells can pass to a mobile phase (F).

1.2.5. Ecophysiology of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

In order to establish a successful culture of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in laboratory, ecophysiological needs have to be considered first, sometimes specific to each species/phylogroup. Commonly, the environmental conditions favorable to the proliferation of *Gambierdiscus* spp. are the following: shallow water habitat (< 50 m), annual water temperatures between 21°C and 31°C (with optimum between 25–29 °C), abundant substrates (*e.g.* macrophytes, algal turfs or rocky sediments) to which

Gambierdiscus cells can attach, low to moderate turbulence, high and stable salinities, actual or attenuated incident light levels (< 10%), and sufficient or elevated nutrient inputs, some of which can be obtained directly from the macrophyte hosts (Litaker et al., 2010).

Xu et al., 2016 studied the influence of environmental variables on *Gambierdiscus* spp. growth and distribution on a total of 17 strains representing eight different species/phylotypes of *Gambierdiscus* using single factor experiments in laboratory. (Xu et al., 2016)

Concerning the salinity experiment, Xu et al., 2016 showed that *Gambierdiscus* spp. can grow in a range of salinities from 20 to 50, with the maximum growth rates observed at salinities of 30-40. Generally *Gambierdiscus* prefer high salinities (28-35) typical of oceanic waters in endemic areas for ciguatera, thus oceanic salinity should sustain growth of most *Gambierdiscus* species. In coastal region affected by freshwater inputs, hyposaline condition may inhibit *Gambierdiscus* survival, even if some *Gambierdiscus* species have good chance of survival or growth (e.g. *G. scabrosus*, *G. carpenteri* and *G. caribaeus*) (Xu et al., 2016).

Concerning salinity preferences, other studies should also be cited. *G. excentricus* species prefers salinities from 36.6 to 36.8-37 (Xu et al., 2016) (Fraga et al., 2011). For *G. scabrosus* the semi-optimal salinity condition falls into a range of 23-35 (Yoshimatsu et al., 2014). The optimum salinity for *G. sp. Vietnam* is comprised within 30 and 35 (Yoshimatsu et al., 2014).

Concerning temperature preferences, other studies should also be cited. *G. excentricus* was found in an area with sea surface temperature from about 18°C to 24°C (Fraga et al., 2011), even though the range for *G. scabrosus* and *G. sp. Vietnam* is from 25°C to 30°C (Roeder et al., 2010) (Yoshimatsu et al., 2014).

Temperature plays an essential role in restricting the distribution of *Gambierdiscus* spp.: the high temperature requirement for its growth explains why this organism, and ciguatera, is endemic in tropical and subtropical areas. However, within the context of climate change, precipitations become less frequent and more intense, usually followed

by longer dry periods. This aspect, along with the global warming, the water stratification and the increased availability of nutrients, are expected to boost dinoflagellate proliferation, even in areas previously considered as non-endemic (Xu et al., 2016).

1.3. Toxins produced by *Gambierdiscus* spp.

1.3.1. Background

Two major groups of toxins are produced by *Gambierdiscus* spp.: ciguatoxins (CTXs), which bioaccumulate in fish and are involved in Ciguatera Fish Poisoning, and maitotoxins (MTXs), one of the most complex non-polymeric natural products known to date. Other bioactive compounds with a polyether structure have been isolated from *Gambierdiscus* cultures as well, e.g. gambierol (Kopljar et al., 2009), gambieric acids (Nagai et al., 1992) gambieroxide (Watanabe et al., 2013) and gambierone (Rodriguez et al., 2015). These findings underscore the still largely untapped chemical diversity produced by *Gambierdiscus* spp. and encourage further chemical characterization of their metabolome (Rodriguez et al., 2015).

1.3.2. Ciguatoxins (CTXs)

1.3.2.1. Background

Ciguatoxins (CTXs) are secondary metabolites, produced by benthic dinoflagellates of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa*, and are the causative agents of Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP). The algal CTXs gradually bioaccumulate in fish flesh through the marine food chain from herbivorous grazers to carnivorous predators. Along with this bioaccumulation, the algal CTXs undergo to metabolisation in fish, resulting in more toxic analogs (Chinain et al., 2010).

Ciguatoxins were first isolated from the moray eel *Gymnothorax javanicus* in 1967 (Scheuer et al., 1967). Subsequently, several CTX analogs have been isolated from biodetritus containing wild *G. toxicus* (Holmes et al., 1991), from toxic strains of cultured

dinoflagellate isolated from different parts of the world (Holmes et al., 1991) or from various ciguateric fish (Legrand et al., 1992).

CTXs are polyethers with a rigid structure, consisting in 13-14 transfused rings fused by ether bonds. To date, numerous CTX analogs have been described and they are grouped into three sub-families according to their geographical origin, *i.e.* Pacific, Caribbean, and Indian CTXs (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Figure 6. Structure of P-CTX-1.

These biotoxins are heat resistant and lipid soluble, so they are not degraded by cooking processes. Among the marine toxins known to date, CTXs are classified as potent, with an LD₅₀ in mice (*i.p.*) equivalent to 0.25, 2.3, 0.9 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ for, respectively, P-CTX-1 (figure 6), P-CTX-2, and P-CTX-3. From our knowledge of the chemical structure of ciguatoxins found at different trophic levels, Murata et al. (1990) concluded that P-CTX-1, the dominant and most potent ciguatoxin, extracted from the moray eel *Gymnothorax javanicus*, arises from the acid-catalyzed spiroisomerization and oxidative modification of P-CTX-4A, produced by the dinoflagellate *G. toxicus*. The degree of oxidation is positively correlated with potency (Lewis et al., 1991): P-CTX-1 was described as more potent than 54-deoxy CTX.

P-CTXs are more potent than C-CTXs and I-CTXs. Less than 1 ng kg^{-1} (kg of human body weight) of P-CTX-1 causes CFP symptoms in humans (Lehane and Lewis, 2000), while concentrations of 1 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of C-CTX-2 and 5 $\mu\text{g kg}^{-1}$ of I-CTXs are required to cause first CFP symptoms (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Table 3. CTXs isolated from fish and microalgal origin (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Origin		Number of rings	Number of carbons	Examples of CTX	Molecular Weigh	Source
Pacific (P-)	Type I	13	60	CTX (CTX1B, CTX-1)	1110.6	carnivorous fish
				CTX2A2 (CTX-2, 52-epi-54-deoxyCTX)	1094.5	carnivorous fish
				CTX2B2 (CTX-3, 54-deoxyCTX)	1094.5	carnivorous fish
				CTX4A	1060.8	<i>G. toxicus</i> , <i>G. polynesiensis</i>
				CTX4B (GTX-4B, Gt 4b)	1060.8	<i>G. toxicus</i> , <i>G. polynesiensis</i> , herbivorous fish
	Type II	13	57	CTX3C	1022.8	<i>G. toxicus</i> , <i>G. polynesiensis</i> , herbivorous fish
			CTX2A1 (2,3-dihydroxyCTX3C)	1056.0	carnivorous fish	
Caribbean (C-)		14	62	CTX-1	1140.7	carnivorous fish
				CTX-2	1140.7	carnivorous fish
Indian (I-)		nd	nd	CTX-1	1140.6	carnivorous fish
				CTX-2	1140.6	carnivorous fish
				CTX-3	1157.6	carnivorous fish
				CTX-4	1157.6	carnivorous fish

Ciguatoxins (CTXs) bind the site 5 of the alpha-subunit of voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSC or Na_v), the same as brevetoxins. LD₅₀ of different CTXs is proportional to their affinity for the VGSCs (Caillaud et al., 2010a). The mechanism of action consists in the activation of VGSCs, causing continuous Na⁺ flux into the cells and triggering several effects at cellular and physiological levels: axonal and Schwann oedema (Benoit et al., 1996), excitability of the membrane, release of neurotransmitters (Molgo et al., 1990), increase of intracellular calcium, blockage of the voltage-gated potassium channels (VGPCs) (Hidalgo et al., 2002). Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) is different from other marine intoxications, due to its chronic long lasting effects. However, all the symptoms elicited during CFP are not exclusively due to the activation of VGSCs: chronic fatigue symptoms, for example, have been related to the high release of nitric oxide (NO).

1.3.2.2. CTX families

Pacific ciguatoxins (P-CTXs)

The chemical structures of a number of Pacific ciguatoxins from fish and *G. toxicus* have been elucidated using NMR techniques. Among the ciguatoxins known so far, P-CTX-1 is considered as the most toxic congener and the principal responsible for the neurological symptoms in the Pacific.

Caribbean ciguatoxins (C-CTXs)

The chemical structures of C-CTX-1 and C-CTX-2, the major ciguatoxins from Caribbean fish, have been elucidated using NMR techniques (Lewis et al., 1998) and additional C-CTX congeners have been described but not structurally characterized (Pottier et al., 2002).

Indian ciguatoxins (I-CTXs)

Four ciguatoxins from the Indian Ocean (I-CTX-1–4) have been isolated from *Lutjanus sebae* (red emperor) and *Lutjanus bohar* (red bass) (Hamilton et al., 2002b) but no chemical structure has been elucidated yet and they are not even well characterized by LC-MS/MS.

Figure 7. Structures of ciguatoxins from the Pacific Ocean and Caribbean Sea. The picture shows P-CTX-1 and P-CTX-3, isolated from fish caught in the Pacific. CTX4B and CTX3C were isolated from *Gambierdiscus* spp. coming from the Pacific. C-CTX-1 (the less energetically favourable epimer C-CTX-2 is shown in the inset). Similarly, P-CTX-2 is the C52 epimer of P-CTX-3. Brevetoxin-2 (PbTx-2) is shown for comparison.

1.3.2.3. Sample preparation for CTX determination

Numerous protocols of sample preparation, to research and/or monitoring purposes, have been reported in the scientific literature for CTX determination, during the last decade. They are addressed for both fish and algal samples (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Sample preparation for CTX determination, in fish matrices, usually follows a general pattern, derived from the first descriptions given by Scheuer's (Lewis et al., 1998) and Yasumoto's teams (Sauviat et al., 2002) in the 1960s. Acetone- or methanol-based extraction is used, allowing lipophilic compounds retrieval, such as CTXs. Acetone extraction being more efficient is preferentially used, and is often carried out two or three consecutive times to increase toxin retrieval. A second step consists in the elimination of fatty acids. It is based upon liquid-liquid partition with hexane, diethyl ether, or chloroform. Fatty acids and CTX content may vary in quantity and quality among fish species, hence, certain conditions of the purification steps have to be modulated according to the origin or the age of the fish.

Sample preparation procedures for CTX determination in microalgae are still based upon the original extraction protocols previously described for CTX characterization from wild and cultured *G. toxicus* (Molgo et al., 1993). The first step consists in extracting cell pellets using methanol (aqueous or absolute) or acetone. According to the aim of the research and the grade of purity required, the resulting crude extracts may be further purified for the separation of CTXs from other concomitant toxins (*e.g.* MTXs) using liquid-liquid solvent partitioning with dichloromethane, hexane, or diethyl ether (Pérez-Arellano et al., 2005), or by high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC) (Molgo et al., 1993).

1.3.2.4. CTX determination methods

When selecting a method for CTX determination, the scope of application should be considered (*e.g.* food safety assessment, research or diagnostic purposes). The development of simple and cost-effective individual tests, such as ready-to-use kits to be used by fishermen and consumers, to check the safety of fishing products, requires

different approaches and costs than the ones employed for the CTX recognition used in research laboratories.

There are a lot of traditional methods, used by indigenous population of ciguateric regions, in order to detect the toxicity in fish. One of those involves the use of ants: if the fish is not contaminated it will be rapidly covered by the ants, while if it is contaminated it will not be exploited. This method was tested by Banner et al. (1963), in order to discover if there is a true relationship between the toxicity of a fish and the behavior of the ants (Banner et al., 1963). The responses given by the study showed that it was not possible to find a relationship. This method was tested again in New Caledonia (Boydron-Le Garrec, 2004) and it gave false-negative results as well.

Scientific methods, developed for CTX determination, can be divided in two sections: biological and chemical methods. It is necessary to make a difference between methods that provide results on toxicity (*e.g.* a cytotoxicity response) from methods that provide the quantification of a specific compound (*e.g.* LC-MS/MS) (). The most frequently used include: *in vivo* mouse bioassay (MBA), bioassays on animal tissues, *in vitro* cell-based assays (CBAs, such as neuro-2a assay), pharmacological receptor-binding assay (RBA), immunological assays and physico-chemical analytical methods (HPLC-UV, HPLC-FLD, LC-MS) (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

a) Biological methods

The first laboratory studies for CTX detection consisted in testing samples on whole animals, both vertebrates and invertebrates. CTXs were tested on cats (Caillaud et al., 2010a), mongooses (Bagnis and Fevai, 1971), chickens (Banner and Boroughs, 1958), mosquitos (Kosaki and Anderson, 1968), larvae of *Diptera* (Chungue et al., 1984), crayfish and other crustaceans (Labrousse and Matile, 1996). Different exposure ways were taken into account: the parenteral route, for example, is one of the most used. It consists in an injection, which could be intraperitoneal, intramuscular or intrathoracic. Another possibility is feeding animals with toxic fish (oral exposure), or adding toxic compounds in their culture medium.

In vivo: Mouse Bioassay (MBA)

The mouse bioassay (MBA), for CTX determination, was first introduced by (Keene et al., 1968) Banner et al., 1960 and it is still the most widely used mammalian *in vivo* model for toxicity screening.

The lethal dose (LD) for Mouse Unit (MU) of a toxin is defined by (Banner et al., 1960) as the minimum dose of fish extract necessary to kill a 20 g mouse in 24 h after *i.p.* injection. Usually MU is used to express the relationship between the dose and the time to death. One MU is equivalent to 5 ng, 18 ng and 48 ng for Pacific CTXs, P-CTX-1, P-CTX-2 and P-CTX-3, respectively and 72 ng for pure Caribbean CTX-1 (Endean et al., 1993). It was formerly suggested that any fish containing above 2.5 MU per 100 g should be avoided from food.

The disadvantages of the MBA are described as follows: (i) requirement of a qualified personnel, (ii) lack of specificity for any group of toxins, (iii) unsuitability, as a market test, for individual CTX detection. However, it remains a toxicological tool that is accessible to many laboratories and is capable of effective clinical recognition (Pottier et al., 2003). Historically, MBA has been widely used for assessing the good experimental separation of CTXs *versus* MTXs (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

	($\mu\text{g}/\text{kg}$)	(ng)		death	death time
CTX-1 ^a	0.25	5	hypothermia below 33°C, piloerection, diarrhoea, lachrymation, hypersalivation, dyspnoea, wobbly upright gait, gasping, terminal convulsions with tail arching, death from respiratory failure	$\log(\text{MU}) = 3.3 \log(1+T^{-1})$	37 min/ ~24 hr
CTX-2 ^a	2.3	9	as for CTX-1, plus progressive hind limb paralysis	$\log(\text{MU}) = 2.4 \log(1+T^{-1})$	53 min/ ~100 hr
CTX-3 ^a	0.9	18	as for CTX-1, plus progressive hind limb paralysis	$\log(\text{MU}) = 3.9 \log(1+T^{-1})$	60 min/ ~26 hr
GTX-3C ^b	1.3	26	–	–	–
GTX-4B ^c	4.0	80	as for CTX-1, plus hind limb paralysis	–	–
MTX-1 ^d	0.05	1	hypothermia, piloerection, dyspnoea, progressive paralysis from hind extending to fore limbs, mild gasping, mild convulsions preceding death >30 sec	$\log(\text{MU}) = 6.7 \log(1+T^{-1})$	72 min/ ~72 hr
MTX-2 ^d	0.08	1.6	as for MTX-1	$\log(\text{MU}) = 4.0 \log(1+T^{-1})$	41 min/ ~72 hr
MTX-3 ^d	~0.1	~2	as for MTX-1	$\log(\text{MU}) = 6.7 \log(1+T^{-1})$	72 min/ ~72 hr
OA ^e	210	4200	hypothermia, hind limb paralysis, dyspnoea and	$\log(\text{MU}) =$	47 min/

Figure 8. Signs of intoxication due to different groups of toxins in mice after *i.p.* injection (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

^a **CTX-1, 2 and 3** (= Ciguatoxin-1, -2 and -3) are from *Gambierdiscus toxicus* (Murata et al., 1990), can accumulate in fish.

^b **GTX-3C** (= Gambierotoxin-3C) is from *Gambierdiscus toxicus* (Satake et al., 1993), can accumulate in fish.

^c **GTX-4B** (= Gambierotoxin-4B) is from *Gambierdiscus toxicus* (Murata et al., 1990), can be accumulated in fish.

^d **MTX-1, 2 and 3** (= Maitotoxin-1, -2 and -3) are from *G. toxicus*, but they are unlikely to accumulate to significant level in fish.

MU= mouse unit, where 1 MU is the LD₅₀ dose for a 20g mouse

T = time to death in hour;

In vitro bioassays: Neuroblastoma neuro-2a (N2a) assay

In vitro cell-based assays (CBAs) provide important tools for studying the effect of toxins in cells, isolated from different tissues, and for comprehending the mechanisms of action in cells that present specific targets (*e.g.* receptors) for the toxin considered. Cells rapidly respond to toxic stress through the alteration of metabolic rates, cell growth, or the transcription of genes that control basic functions. Consequently, CBAs based on different cell models have been developed for the analysis of food designated for human consumption (Boydron-Le Garrec, 2004).

Neuroblastoma neuro-2a (N2a) is a suitable cell model to evaluate numerous neurotoxins which target voltage-gated sodium channels (VGSCs), such as brevetoxins, ciguatoxins, tetrodotoxins or saxitoxins. Binding of neurotoxins to their receptors on the VGSCs modulates the conformation of these proteins, which cause an activation or blockage of the sodium influx (Eisenbrand et al., 2002).

For CTX determination, N2a cells have to be pretreated with ouabain (O), an inhibitor of Na⁺/K⁺-ATPase pump, and veratridine (V), which holds sodium channels in an open position (Catterall, 1980). The combined action of O and V results in an increase of intracellular Na⁺ concentration, which may lead to cell death, depending on the concentrations tested. The addition of VGSC-activator toxins (e.g. ciguatoxins and brevetoxins) increases the toxic effects induced by O and V, leading to higher N2a mortality, with respect to the control. After 20-24 h incubation, cell viability can be assessed using a colorimetric assay (e.g. MTT assay).

The main advantages of the neuro-2a assay, for CTX determination, are: (i) easy handling of the N2a cell line, (ii) high sensitivity to CTXs (in the range of few fg cell⁻¹) and (iii) the suitability for routine screening purposes (Hardison et al., 2016). Nevertheless, this assay takes long time (about 3 days), and its lack of a universally standardized protocol. Furthermore, neuro-2a cells have to be maintained (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Immunoassays

Immunoassays have been considered as a very promising approach for designing a rapid, reliable and cost-effective method for mass screening of fish, prior to consumption, mainly because of their specificity. However, synthesis of specific antibodies (Abs) against CTXs has been prevented by CTXs' extreme scarcity and chemical complexity.

From an immunological point of view, CTXs are considered to be haptens, low molecular weight compounds, which contain one or more antigenic determinants (epitopes), which are able to trigger an immunologic response, only if they are covalently conjugated to a large molecule acting as an immunogenic carrier (Hardison et al., 2016).

Immunoassays present the advantages of being rapid, simple and low-costing, making them suitable for monitoring the toxicity of fish, prior to consumption. Nevertheless, its applicability should not only rely on the specificity of the Abs for their target molecules, but also on the availability of simple and rapid sample clean-up and concentration procedures for sample preparation.

Receptor Binding Assay

The receptor binding assay (RBA) represents another method for estimating CTX concentrations in fish and algal matrices. The RBA designed for CTXs measures the binding competition between the ciguatoxins, present in the sample, and a labeled brevetoxins (PbTx) standard (radioactive or fluorescent) for the voltage-gated sodium channel, as they share the same molecular target (site-5 of the alpha subunit). Hence, CTXs present in the samples, compete quantitatively with the PbTx standard for the binding site, and, as a consequence, the binding of the labeled PbTx is inversely related to the concentration of unlabeled CTXs.

A **radioactivity-based** receptor binding assay (RBA_(R)) was developed by Caillaud et al. (2010). Briefly, rat brain synaptosomes containing Na⁺ channels are incubated with a fixed amount of tritiated brevetoxin-3 ([³H]-PbTx-3). Then the samples containing CTXs are added for binding competition. RBA_(R) was successfully applied for monitoring programs, on ciguatera risk, in three islands of French Polynesia: Tubuai, Raivavae and Nuku-Hiva (Hollenberg and Nexø, 1981). Indeed, RBA proved to be a very valuable, suitable and sensitive tool, for detecting ciguatoxins, in all stages of the trophic chain of ciguatera.

Very recently, a **fluorescence-based** receptor binding assay (RBA_(F)) has been developed for CTX determination by (Litaker et al., 2009). The assay is based on the competition between the CTXs, present in the sample, and a fluorescently labeled brevetoxin-2 (PbTx-2) for the binding site. The main advantage of this assay is the way of labeling the brevetoxin standard: the utilization of fluorescence instead of radioactivity enlarges the applicability of the assay in facilities not certified to use radioisotopes. In addition, the assay is cost-effective, allows high sample throughput, is stable over long periods of time

and is rapid (< 3 h). The only disadvantage observed with the RBA_(F), and the same is true for the RBA_(R), is that the detection limit is 10-fold higher than the CBA-N2a. However this method was successfully used to detect and quantify CTXs in fish extracts, and the results were in accordance with CBA-N2a, RBA_(R) assays and LC-MS/MS analyses (Hardison et al., 2016).

b) Chemical methods

High-performance liquid chromatography coupled with UV detection (HPLC-UV)

Since most CTXs do not possess distinctive chromophore groups in their structure (*e.g.* series of conjugated double bonds), they do not strongly absorb radiation over the ultraviolet/visible (UV/VIS) region. As a consequence, detection of CTXs have to be carried at 210–215 nm, a poorly sensitive and non-selective range for detection.

Although HPLC-UV method is applicable to a wide variety of toxins, it is limited by: (i) low sensitivity and (ii) interference of naturally occurring compounds with similar retention times as the toxins (Hardison et al., 2016).

High-performance liquid chromatography coupled with fluorescence detection (HPLC-FLD)

Some of the CTX analogs (*e.g.* P-CTX-1) present a primary hydroxyl group on the side chain. This functional group can be easily derivative into a fluorescent ester, so that high-performance liquid chromatography coupled with fluorescence detection (HPLC-FLD) becomes suitable for CTX determination (Tang et al., 2015). Since a primary hydroxyl group may often be present in compounds from such biological matrices, an additional clean-up step is required, *e.g.* solid-phase extraction (SPE).

Different procedures of sample preparation have been developed for CTXs quantification, using this methodology, both for microalgae and fish matrices (Pauillac et al., 1997) (Legrand et al., 1992) (Yasumoto et al., 1993). Unfortunately, the HPLC-FLD cannot be used in routine monitoring programs, since these toxins are extremely potent, causing

intoxication at very low amounts (e.g. 0.01 ppb P-CTX-1, 0.1 ppb C-CTX-1), so this method is not sufficiently sensitive for CTX determination in biological samples. Moreover, this detection mode cannot allow the detection of CTXs that do not have a primary hydroxyl group (e.g. P-CTX-3C).

High-performance liquid chromatography coupled with mass spectrometry detection (LC-MS)

The principle of coupling liquid chromatography with mass spectrometry detection is the following: as the components elute from the HPLC column, they are ionized in the source of the spectrometer. Each ion can subsequently be fragmented (tandem mass spectrometry MS/MS) and each ion, parent and/or fragment(s), is detected, thanks to its mass/charge state (m/z) ratio. Data are then translated and processed in order to obtain a mass spectra of each separated compound, at a specific retention time.

Recently, Yogi et al. (2011) developed a sensible HPLC-MS/MS method capable of detecting and quantifying 16 Pacific ciguatoxins and related polyethers (gambierol, gambieric acids A and B) using 14 reference toxins obtained by either chemical synthesis or isolation from natural sources.

HPLC-MS was also applied for the characterization of Caribbean ciguatoxins (C-CTXs). Pottier et al. (2002) identified 12 C-CTXs analogs from a horse-eye jack (*Caranx latus*) that was previously purified with size-exclusion chromatography.

Indian ciguatoxins (I-CTXs) have been found via LC-MS techniques in two fish species: the red bass *Lutjanus bohar* and the red emperor *Lutjanus sebae* (Hamilton et al., 2002a; Hamilton et al., 2002b).

Table 4. Principal ciguatoxin congeners analyzed by LC-MS with their molecular ion $[M+H]^+$ masses (Caillaud et al., 2010a).

Name	Alternative name	Molecular ion $[M + H]^+$	Source
Pacific ciguatoxins			
P-CTX-1	CTX1B	1111.6	Carnivorous fish
P-CTX-2	CTX2A2; 52- <i>epi</i> -54-deoxyCTX	1095.5	Carnivorous fish
P-CTX-3	CTX2B2; 54-deoxyCTX	1095.5	Carnivorous fish
49- <i>epi</i> -CTX-3C	CTX-3B	1023.6	<i>G. toxicus</i>
M- <i>seco</i> -CTX-3C		1041.6	<i>G. toxicus</i>
CTX-3C		1023.6	<i>G. toxicus</i>
2,3-dihydroxyCTX-3C	CTX-2A1	1057.6	Carnivorous fish/ <i>G. toxicus</i>
β1-hydroxyCTX-3C	CTX-2C1	1039.5	Carnivorous fish
CTX-4B	GT-4B	1061.6	<i>G. toxicus</i> Herbivorous fish
52- <i>epi</i> -ciguatoxin-4B	CTX-4A; GT-4A	1061.6	<i>G. toxicus</i>
Caribbean ciguatoxins			
C-CTX-1		1141.6	Carnivorous fish
C-CTX-2	56- <i>epi</i> -C-CTX-1	1141.6	Carnivorous fish
C-CTX-1127		1127.6	Carnivorous fish
C-CTX-1143		1143.6	Carnivorous fish
C-CTX-1157		1157.6	Carnivorous fish
C-CTX-1159		1159.6	Carnivorous fish
Indian ciguatoxins			
I-CTX-1		1141.6	Carnivorous fish
I-CTX-2		1141.6	Carnivorous fish
I-CTX-3		1157.6	Carnivorous fish
I-CTX-4		1157.6	Carnivorous fish

In summary, LC-MS techniques represent a very useful tool for (1) the identification and characterization of new CTX congeners from different matrices; (2) the quantification of known analogs (by tandem mass spectrometry MS/MS). However, the limit of detection is still not sufficient to meet the requirements of the safety limits (0.01 ng g^{-1} for P-CTX-1 and 0.1 ng g^{-1} for C-CTX-1) (Hamilton et al., 2002a). Improvements in instrumentation and in sample preparation will allow the routine application of LC-MS techniques to overcome some matrix effects from fish samples and decrease the limits of detection and quantification.

1.3.2.5. EU and US regulation

Concerning the Ciguatera Fish Poisoning (CFP) issue, the EU regulation states as follows: “Fishery products containing biotoxins such as ciguatoxin or muscle-paralysing toxins must not be placed on the market”. This text was further extended to “ciguatoxins or other toxins dangerous to human health” (1021/2008, 2008). EC No 853/2004 and EC No

1021/2008. Contrarily to the expectations, European regulation does not clearly provide the reference analytical method for CTX detection, neither the sanitary threshold. Of note, within the EU, national regulations specifically addressing CFP issue do exist in some countries (e.g. some French overseas departments located in ciguatera endemic areas, such as French Polynesia, la Réunion, la Martinique). The French legislation directly incorporated the European directive, which is applicable for products imported in France from outside the EU and permits the importation of certain marine species off a positive list. Groupers, snappers, barracuda and surgeonfish are banned for sale in French Polynesia (Dickey and Plakas, 2010).

Figure 9. Example of outreach and educational materials developed for CFP (Bagnis et al., 1992).

In the United States of America, CFP is reportable to the health authorities in various states. Suspected cases are then investigated by public health officials and confirmed cases are recorded in the state's registry of reportable/notifiable diseases. Determining the source of the fish purchased or the area from which the fish was caught is important for preventing additional cases that may occur when a large, recreationally caught fish is shared or when a wholesaler may have shipped toxic fish to other areas for resale (Friedman et al., 2008). The FDA's Center for Food Safety and Nutrition (CFSAN) conducts research on CFP and collaborates with academic and government counterparts, as part of

its mission to protect and advance public health. The FDA has developed methods to screen and confirm the ciguatoxicity of CFP-implicated fish remnants, and collects data on ciguatoxic fish species, toxin concentrations associated with human illness, and potential biomarkers of CFP in human body fluids. Furthermore, the National Oceanic and Atmospheric Administration (NOAA) Centers for Coastal Ocean Sciences (NCCOS) also conducts research on ciguatoxicity of fish, as part of its mission to provide scientific information that addresses society's environmental, economic and social goals, and promotes the health of the ecosystem and natural resources.

The suggested threshold for CTXs is 0.01 µg P-CTX-1 equivalents per kg of fish flesh, which corresponds to one tenth of the dose estimated to cause the slightest symptoms in humans (Friedman et al., 2008). This dose is so low that highly sensitive and specific methods have to be developed for the detection of very low CTX concentration in complex matrices such as fish.

1.3.3. Maitotoxins (MTXs)

1.3.3.1. Background

Maitotoxins (MTXs) are a family of ladder-shaped polyether compounds produced by *Gambierdiscus* spp., soluble in water, which may be found in the viscera of fish (Friedman et al., 2008).

Three MTX analogs are known to date: maitotoxin-1 (MTX-1, 3422 Da, as the disodium salt), maitotoxin-2 (MTX-2, 3298 Da, as the monosodium salt) and maitotoxin-3 (MTX-3, 1060 Da, as the disodium salt). The structural elucidation by NMR technique has been obtained only for MTX-1. MTX-1 is the largest non-biopolymer molecule known so far: it possesses a weight of 3422 Da ($C_{164}H_{256}O_{68}S_2Na_2$, as the disodium salt) (). MTX-1 (figure 10) was first discovered from the surgeonfish *Ctenochaetus striatus* and it was described as one of the causative toxins of ciguatera. It was named after the Tahitian name of the surgeonfish "*maito*" (Yasumoto and Kanno, 1976). MTX-1 and MTX-3 are di-sulphated polyethers whereas MTX-2 is mono-sulphated. The sulphated groups seem to play a role

in the toxicity of these molecules, since an *in vitro* study by (Murata et al., 1993) showed that solvolysis reduces MTX toxic effects.

Figure 10. Structure of maitotoxin (MTX-1)(Yasumoto and Kanno, 1976).

MTX has extremely strong biological activity: its toxicity against mice (LD_{50}) by intraperitoneal injection is 50 ng kg^{-1} (Murata et al., 1991).

So far, this lethal capacity makes MTX amongst the most potent marine toxins known to date (Murata and Yasumoto, 2000). However, their low capacity of bioaccumulation in fish tissues and their low potency by oral route suggest that MTXs are unlikely to produce human illness (Ohizumi et al., 1983).

MTX increases intracellular calcium concentration ($[Ca^{2+}]_i$) (Yasumoto et al., 1976) inducing many responses at the cellular and physiological level:

Mechanical response: MTX causes a sustained contraction of isolated rabbit aorta at concentrations above $10^{-10} \text{ g mL}^{-1}$. The MTX-induced contraction lasts for at least 3 hours. Contractile response increases with MTX concentrations in a dose-dependent manner (Lewis, 2006).

Calcium content: Gusovsky and Daly (1990) studied Ca^{2+} content of the isolated rabbit aorta after 30 min exposure with MTX ($10^{-8} \text{ g mL}^{-1}$) and compared it with its constrictive effect. The Ca^{2+} content was increased by MTX from 1.45 to $1.90 \text{ } \mu\text{mol g}^{-1}$ wet weight. Under the same experimental conditions, MTX ($10^{-8} \text{ g mL}^{-1}$) caused a marked contraction (Ohizumi and Yasumoto, 1983).

Na⁺/K⁺ATPase: The effects of MTX (ranging from 3×10^{-10} to 3×10^{-7} g mL⁻¹) and ouabain on Na⁺ and K⁺ ATPase activities were examined using purified enzyme preparations, obtained from porcine cerebral cortex. Ouabain (10^{-5} M) inhibited the Na⁺ and K⁺ stimulated ATPase activity, whereas MTX had little effect on the activity at any of the concentrations used (Ohizumi and Yasumoto, 1983). As a consequence, MTXs have been extensively used as a pharmacological tool for research on calcium-dependent mechanisms (Ohizumi and Yasumoto, 1983).

Many studies have been carried out in order to try to underline the MTXs mechanism of action. Gutierrez et al. (1997) demonstrated that MTX-induced Ca²⁺ influx depends on the presence of extracellular Ca²⁺ and potentiated by an increase in [iCa²⁺] (Ohizumi and Yasumoto, 1983). Mouse bioassay signs were shown to be similar among the three MTXs described, hypothesizing a similar mode of action of the three MTXs congeners described (Gusovsky and Daly, 1990).

Figure 11. Comparison of molecular lengths of polyether/polyhydroxy compounds. All these polyketide metabolites are products of microalgae. The arrow shows the thickness of the lipid bilayer membrane (Gutierrez et al., 1997).

1.3.3.2. Sample preparation for MTX determination

Isolation of MTXs from the algal cells is a hard task, since, as evidenced by Murata and Yasumoto (2000), under usual conditions for preparative HPLC, the peaks given by MTXs are neither clear nor reproducible. This is probably due to the coexistence of a polar polyhydroxyl part, including two sulphate esters, and a hydrophobic cyclic part (Holmes et al., 1991).

For toxin extraction, Murata and Yasumoto (2000) suggested a particular procedure. Briefly, *Gambierdiscus* extracts are sonicated in absolute methanol for 30 minutes with an extraction volume (V_e) proportional to total cell number ($V_e = 1 \text{ mL}$ equivalent to 10×10^6 cells). Five minute centrifugation at 4°C , at 600 g, is then carried out to obtain a methanol extract. The extraction procedure is repeated three times for *Gambierdiscus* extracts, one with absolute methanol and two with aqueous methanol (50:50, v/v). Supernatants are then dried at 40°C and stored at -20°C until analysis.

Figure 12. Purification scheme for MTXs (Murata and Yasumoto, 2000).

A purification scheme was established by Caillaud et al. (2010) after testing HPLC columns for many years (figure 12). In their work, the combined use of three kinds of reversed phase columns is considered a key process for purification. The trimethylsilyl-substituted silica gel (TMS), showed the best separation of MTXs from impurities.

1.3.3.3. Toxicological assays for MTX detection

The mouse bioassay displayed characteristic symptoms such as piloerection, reduced body temperature, dyspnea, progressive paralysis, gasping and longer minimum death time compared to CTXs (Murata and Yasumoto, 2000). Functional assays like a cell-based assay using the F-actin microfilament distribution (Murata and Yasumoto, 2000), an

immunoassay, using maitotoxin-specific antibodies (Holmes et al., 1990) and a fluorimetric assay, based on membrane potential measurement for the detection of ions influx induced toxins (Diogene et al., 1995) have also been developed for MTX detection. Bignami et al. (1996) developed a neuroblastoma neuro-2a cell-based assay, capable of detecting both ciguatoxins and maitotoxins. Ouabain and veratridine were used to enhance the activation of sodium channels such as caused by CTXs, while SK&F96365 was used to block the increase of intracellular calcium such as caused by MTXs.

1.3.4. Other bioactive compounds

a) Gambierol

Gambierol was isolated and structurally characterized by Satake et al. (1993) from cultured cells of *Gambierdiscus toxicus* (Louzao et al., 2006). This compound inhibits voltage-gated potassium ion channels (VGPCs) at nanomolar concentrations and shows potent acute neurotoxicity in mice (Caillaud et al., 2009).

b) Gambieric acids

Gambieric acid A, B, C and D were isolated from *G. toxicus* by Nagai et al. (1992). Gambieric acids A and B have brevetoxin-type structures consisting of nine contiguous ether rings, and one isolated tetrahydrofuran. Gambieric acids C and D are 3-methylhemiglutarates of gambieric acids A and B. All Gambieric acids have highly potent antifungal properties.

c) Gambieroxide

Gambieroxide was isolated from benthic dinoflagellate *G. toxicus*. The chemical structure of gambieroxide is similar to that of yessotoxin, one of the lipophilic toxins produced by the dinoflagellate *Protoceratium reticulatum* (Watanabe et al., 2013). It is suggested that Gambieroxide shows biological activities similar to yessotoxin (Satake et al., 1993a).

d) Gambierone

Rodriguez et al. (2015) isolated a new ladder-shaped toxin named gambierone from laboratory cultures of *G. belizeanus* CCMP401. The structure, elucidated by NMR, is presented in figure 13.

Figure 13. Chemical structure of gambierone(Fuwa, 2016).

Since Gambierone was isolated from a hydrophilic fraction, which could contain MTX, (Watanabe et al., 2013) wanted to determine whether the molecule was active on sodium channels (CTX-like effect) or would open calcium pores (MTX-like effect). Results proved that Gambierone promotes the appearance of sodium currents at hyperpolarized potentials, such as CTX3C, although with much less potency, and does not show any MTX-like effect on calcium levels, hence excluding the possible functional relationship with MTX or analogs.

CHAPTER TWO

OBJECTIVES AND STRATEGIES

2.1. Focus on the four *Gambierdiscus* strains present in this study

The strains present in this study were the following ones: *G. excentricus* VGO 791, *G. excentricus* VGO 792, *G. scabrosus* KW07922_1 and *G. sp.* Vietnam. These four strains were chosen among the culture collection at Phycotoxins laboratory (IFREMER, Nantes) for two main reasons: their phylogenetic distance and their toxicity emerged in previous studies. Figure 14 shows the phylogenetic distance between *Gambierdiscus* species according to Xu et al. (2014).

G. excentricus is a recently described species, with strains isolated first from the Canaries (Rodriguez et al., 2015) and subsequently from Brazil (Rodriguez et al., 2015) (Fraga et al., 2011). Concerning this species, CTX- and MTX-production of three strains from the Canaries (VGO 790, VGO 791, VGO 792) have been evaluated by Fraga et al. (2011) using a modified neuro-2a assay (Nascimento et al., 2012), and ranged, respectively, between 0.37 - 1.10 pg CTX1B eq cell⁻¹ and 0.48 - 1.38 ng MTX eq cell⁻¹ (Fraga et al., 2011). CTX-toxicity data for this species are particularly interesting because they range in a similar order as *G. polynesiensis* TB-92, the most ciguatoxic strain known to date (mouse bioassay: 1500 x 10⁻⁴ MU 1000 cells⁻¹ (Nascimento et al., 2015) and receptor-binding assay (RBA): 11.9 pg CTX3C eq cell⁻¹).

The strain KW070922_1 was isolated from Japan and belongs to a recently described species named *G. scabrosus* (Caillaud et al., 2010a), previously reported as *G. sp.* type 1 (Nishimura et al., 2013). For this particular strain, a previous study realized by Nishimura et al. (2013) showed, on the mouse bioassay, a low Dichloromethane Soluble Fraction

(DSF)-toxicity of 20×10^{-4} MU 1000 cells⁻¹ and a low Methanol Soluble Fraction (MSF)-toxicity of 67×10^{-4} MU 1000 cells⁻¹.

G. sp. Vietnam was isolated from *Avrainvillea sp.* (Chlorophytes) in Cau Island, Vietnam (Chinain et al., 1999) and it is a strain for which species determination is still underway. For this particular strain, a previous study conducted by Nishimura et al. (2014) showed the presence of various CTX congeners using LC-MS/MS techniques : putative 2,3-dihydroxy CTX3C, CTX3C and less significant amounts of CTX4A and CTX4B. No MTX-production data are available to date for this strain (The et al., 2008).

Figure 14. Bayesian inference (BI) phylogeny generated using the D8-D10 region of the LSU rRNA gene of DNA of *Gambierdiscus* species/phylotypes (Roeder et al., 2010). The figure shows the phylogenetic distance between the strains analyzed in this thesis, except for *G. sp. Vietnam*.

2.2. Objectives

Dinoflagellates of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* produce several toxin groups (including ciguatoxins, CTXs, and maitotoxins, MTXs), some of which are implicated in ciguatera poisoning from fish consumption. Although the phenomenon of ciguatera has long been known in the tropics, and although the disease is a major issue at the international level in terms of consumer health and food safety, there is a large gap in the knowledge of the components involved, their responsiveness and detection. Moreover, the geographical extension of the organisms involved in CFP, listed recently in the Eastern Atlantic Ocean and in the Mediterranean Sea, requires an additional effort to describe the toxin profiles of these new populations.

The main aim of this study was to compare growth and MTX-toxicity of four different strains in culture at Phycotoxins laboratory (IFREMER, Nantes): *G. excentricus* VGO 791, *G. excentricus* VGO 792, *G. scabrosus* KW07922_1, *G. sp.* Vietnam. For growth comparison, maximum growth rates of semi-continuous batch cultures have been calculated using Multisizer™ 3 data. For comparison of MTX-toxicity, dose-response curves of partially purified extracts on neuro-2a cell viability have been traced.

The challenges of this thesis were: (1) the establishment of large-scale laboratory cultures for toxin isolation, engraved by the benthic/epiphytic behavior of the dinoflagellate; (2) the sample preparation from pellet harvesting until the purified toxins, focusing on MTXs; (3) the identification of the compounds responsible for toxicity using a bioguided fractionation approach.

Further studies have the aim of clarifying the toxic profile of CTXs and MTXs present in *Gambierdiscus* spp. cultures using the bioguided fractionation approach coupled with LC-HRMS and LC-MS/MS analyses.

2.3. Strategies

2.3.1. Large-scale cultures for toxin purification

As the dinoflagellates of the genera *Gambierdiscus* and *Fukuyoa* exhibit a benthic and epiphytic behavior and a certain variability of environmental and nutritional needs within species, the cultivation of these micro-organisms in laboratory is not a simple task.

For a successful establishment of large-scale cultures for toxin isolation, large surfaces have to be made available for colonization and an optimal combination of nutrient (culture media) and culture conditions (temperature, salinity, irradiance) has to be developed. In order to reach a consistent biomass, different strategies were adopted.

a) Horizontal culture flasks

The horizontal culture flasks have the main advantage of providing a well-defined surface and homogeneous incident light from the top. In this study, Corning CellBIND® flasks with vented caps and a treated polystyrene surface of 225 cm² were adopted in thanks to their previously tested suitability for proliferation of benthic/epiphytic cells: (i) the vented caps allow gas exchanges; (ii) the hydrophilic surface promotes cell adhesion.

b) Glass round-bottomed flask with gentle air bubbling

Such a large number of culture flasks occupies a lot of shelf space in the culture room and make the inoculation and harvesting steps not simple to handle and extremely time demanding. Hence, the possibility of replacing several flasks with a glass round-bottomed flask of higher capacity (4 or 10 L) was examined. A gentle air flow was introduced in the water column with 0.2 µm filters at the inlet and at the outlet without disturbing cell attachment to the surface. This strategy has the following advantages: i) no CO₂ limitation and ii) homogeneity of the composition in the medium thanks to air bubbling; iii) large available surface and volume capacity; iv) reduced shelf space requirement in the culture room; v) easier cell harvesting, vi) reduced cost (glass round-bottomed flasks can be

cleaned, autoclaved and re-utilized). The main disadvantage is the loss of homogeneity of light irradiance, due to the fact that in Ifremer laboratory light source is located at the top.

c) Horizontal plastic bags with gentle air bubbling

A horizontal plastic bag meets the requirement of a high-capacity container (5 L volume) and the introduction of air bubbling presents the advantages described above. Two main improvements can be highlighted: i) homogeneity of light irradiance and ii) 3 fold increase of the surface/volume ratio, which should translate in higher cell densities. Nevertheless, this strategy meets other difficulties such as the requirement of more shelf space in the culture room. Preliminary trials being conducted on one strain (*G. australes* CCMP 1653), seem to be promising, suggesting the pertinence of this strategy for the cultivation of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

2.3.2. Sample preparation

As ciguatoxins and maitotoxins could both cause neuro-2a cell death, the first aim of sample preparation is to separate these two families of compounds. In order to achieve this goal, different physico-chemical proprieties were exploited: lipophilicity and molecule size. Lipophilic CTXs were partitioned in the organic phase (dichloromethane) and amphiphilic MTXs were partitioned in the aqueous methanol phase, as described by (Roeder et al., 2010). Subsequently, the efficacy of size-exclusion chromatography (Sephadex™ LH-20) as a purification step for the aq. methanol soluble fraction (MSF) was evaluated. Size-exclusion Chromatography (SEC), also known as gel filtration, is a technique of separation that depends on the relative size or hydrodynamic volume of a macromolecule. Also the average pore size of the packing has to be underlined in order to better understand the column's properties (Xu et al., 2014). Molecules which have larger diameter than that of the pores within the resin material travel quickly through the column and elute first. Consequently, small molecules, which can enter resin pores, elute later (Satake et al., 1993b). Therefore, SEC is a useful tool to fractionate polymers and to separate small molecules from complex polymeric or biogenic matrices (Barth et al.,

1994). MTX-1 is a large polyether compound with a mass > 3000 Da. MTX-2 seems to have very high mass as well, while MTX-3 has been reported to have approximately 3-fold smaller mass (1060 Da, disodium salt). With the LH-20 approach, we expected to separate our compounds of interest, MTX-1, -2 and/or analogs, if present, elute early, while MTX-3 and/or analogs, elute later.

CHAPTER THREE

MATERIALS AND METHODS

3.1. Laboratory cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

Collection of field samples containing *Gambierdiscus* spp. is the first step to establish monoclonal cultures in laboratory. *Gambierdiscus* spp. can be found on small mixed seaweeds and turf in grooves or they can be collected from tidal pools on the rocks during low tide or from drifting seaweeds very close to the coast. All the field samples have to be transported in Falcon tubes (50 mL) or in plastic bottles (Wu, 2003); (Barth et al., 1994). Once reached the laboratory, single cells are isolated from field samples with a capillary pipette (Rhodes et al., 2014) or using modified pickers (Fraga et al., 2011). Hence, isolated cells are incubated in microwell plates in a sterile culture medium prepared with natural seawater (possibly collected from the same area in which the strain was found) supplemented with diluted nutrients and without silica (Fraga et al., 2011). After some cell divisions, cells are inoculated in more voluminous wells and, subsequently, they are periodically re-inoculated with enriched culture medium in containers which have always more and more capacity.

3.1.1. Culture conditions

The choice of suitable culture conditions for *Gambierdiscus* spp. was not easy because strains cultivated at Phycotoxins laboratory (IFREMER, Nantes) belong to different species and come from places in the world that have very different climatic and environmental conditions.

Initial trials conducted at Phycotoxins laboratory (IFREMER, Nantes) led to the selection of L₁ medium (Rhodes et al., 2014). The L₁ medium is a modification of f/2 containing more trace elements (Fraga et al., 2011) (see below the composition Table 5).

Table 5. Composition of L₁ culture medium (Guillard et al., 1993).

Component	Stock solution (g/L in water)	Quantity	Molar concentration in final medium
NaNO ₃	75.00	1 mL	8.82 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
NaH ₂ PO ₄ ·H ₂ O	5.00	1 mL	3.62 × 10 ⁻⁵ M
Na ₂ SiO ₃ ·9H ₂ O	30.0	1 mL	1.06 × 10 ⁻⁴ M
Trace element solution	(see below)	1 mL	---
Vitamin solution	(see below)	0.5 mL	---
<i>Trace Element solution</i>			
Na ₂ EDTA·2H ₂ O	---	4.36 g	1.17 × 10 ⁻⁵ M
FeCl ₃ ·6H ₂ O	---	3.15 g	1.17 × 10 ⁻⁵ M
MnCl ₂ ·4H ₂ O	178.10	1 mL	9.09 × 10 ⁻⁷ M
ZnSO ₄ ·7H ₂ O	23.00	1 mL	8.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
CoCl ₂ ·6H ₂ O	11.90	1 mL	5.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
CuSO ₄ ·5H ₂ O	2.50	1 mL	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
Na ₂ MoO ₄ ·2H ₂ O	19.90	1 mL	8.22 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
H ₂ SeO ₃	1.29	1 mL	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
NiSO ₄ ·6H ₂ O	2.63	1 mL	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
Na ₃ VO ₄	1.84	1 mL	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
K ₂ CrO ₄	1.94	1 mL	1.00 × 10 ⁻⁸ M
<i>Vitamin solution</i>			
Thiamine·HCl (vit. B1)	---	200 mg	2.96 × 10 ⁻⁷ M
Biotin (vit. H)	0.1	10 mL	2.05 × 10 ⁻⁹ M
Cyanocobalamin (vit. B ₁₂)	1.0	1 mL	3.96 × 10 ⁻¹⁰ M

In this study, L₁ medium is prepared using filtered (0.2 µm) natural seawater from Mediterranean Sea (adjusted salinity of 33 psu), without the addition of silica, and is supplemented with soil extract (1 mL L⁻¹) in order to have an additional source of organic elements. The soil extract is prepared mixing one volume of soil from *Parc de Brière* (Loire Atlantique department, France) in two volumes of water. This mixture is first centrifuged to remove large particles, and then filtered several times until filtration at 0.22 µm which guarantees the sterility of the solution.

The strains have been cultivated in an incubator (small-scale cultures) and in a thermostatic room (large-scale cultures) at 25°C, with an irradiance of 100 µmol photons m⁻² s⁻¹ and a photoperiod of 12 D / 12 N.

3.2.2. Small-scale cultures: growth rate determination

In order to determine the maximum growth rates during the exponential growth phase, *Gambierdiscus* cells were grown in semi-continuous batch cultures as previously described by Guillard and Hargraves (1993). Briefly, all the cultures were acclimated to the culture conditions specific to the laboratory in horizontal 75 cm² culture flasks (Corning® CellBIND®) for several months prior to experimentation. *Gambierdiscus* cells were inoculated in 200 mL of culture medium at an initial concentration of ~100-200 cells mL⁻¹ and incubated at randomly determined sites in the incubator.

Figure 15. Small-scale cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in horizontal 75 cm² culture flasks (Corning® CellBIND®).

An aliquot of the cultures was taken every 3-4 days during a period of 68-78 days (n = 13-15 samplings, at least three generations) and analyzed for cell concentration (cells mL⁻¹) and mean cellular biovolume (Estimated Spherical Volumes, ESV, µm³ cell⁻¹) using a

Multisizer™ 3 Coulter Counter® (Beckman Coulter, Georgia, USA) particle counter equipped with a 280 µm aperture tube and a 1 mL sample volume. The total volume of cells per liter of culture media ($L_{\text{cells}} L_{\text{culture}}^{-1}$) was then calculated. Cells were kept in the exponential growth phase as follows: cultures were transferred to new medium previously adjusted to the appropriate temperature (1 to 10 dilution) when cell concentration reached ~1000-2000 cells mL⁻¹ and, thus, they never experienced nutrient or CO₂ limitation (Guillard and Hargraves, 1993; Hardison et al., 2012; Hardison et al., 2013; Hardison et al., 2014). Maximum growth rates (μ_{max} , d⁻¹) and associated standard errors were calculated by linear regressions of the natural log of $L_{\text{cells}} L_{\text{culture}}^{-1}$ (biovolume) versus time after correcting for serial culture dilutions (Kibler et al., 2012). The corresponding doubling time was calculated using the following formula:

$$T_d = \ln(2) \mu_{\text{max}}^{-1}.$$

3.1.3. Large-scale cultures: toxin purification

One of the aims of this study was to establish large-scale cultures of four *Gambierdiscus* strains for toxin purification. Given the benthic/epiphytic behavior of *Gambierdiscus* spp., the most important aspect to take into account is the surface available for cell proliferation. In order to reach a consistent biomass, different strategies were adopted.

a) Horizontal culture flasks

Several flasks (225 cm² surface, Corning CellBIND®) for each strain were cultured in parallel in the same thermostatic room, under the same experimental conditions.

Figure 16. Large-scale cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in horizontal 225 cm² culture flasks (Corning® CellBIND®).

In particular, 30 flasks were prepared for *G. sp. Vietnam* and *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1, using 25 mL inoculum in 275 mL fresh culture medium (1 to 12 dilution) and 15 flasks were prepared for *G. excentricus* strains (VGO 791 and VGO 792), using 100 mL inoculum and 150 mL culture medium (1 to 2.5 dilution) in reason of their slower growth and lower cell densities. The number of flasks was subsequently reduced when promising results were obtained with glass round-bottomed flasks.

b) Glass round-bottomed flask with gentle air bubbling

The possibility of replacing several flasks with a glass round-bottomed flask with higher capacity (4 or 10 L) was examined.

G. sp. Vietnam and *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 generally reach high cell densities in our laboratory conditions, regardless of the substrate used; hence, cells were inoculated in 10 L glass round-bottomed flasks filled with 5 L fresh medium.

Figure 17. Large-scale cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in 10 L glass round-bottomed flasks with gentle air bubbling.

As *G. excentricus* VGO 791 and VGO 792 reach lower cell densities and are less keen to adapt to glass substrates, cells were initially inoculated in 4 L glass round-bottomed flasks filled with 2 L fresh medium. Only *G. excentricus* VGO 792 successfully adapted to the glass round-bottomed flask system and a subsequent inoculum in a 10 L glass round-bottomed flask was possible.

c) Horizontal plastic bags with gentle air bubbling

The pertinence of cultivating *Gambierdiscus* spp. in horizontal plastic bags with air bubbling was examined. Preliminary trials have been conducted on one strain (*G. australes* CCMP 1653).

Figure 18. Large-scale culture of *Gambierdiscus* spp. in a horizontal plastic bag with gentle air bubbling.

3.2. Harvesting of *Gambierdiscus* cells

The harvesting of *Gambierdiscus* cells occurred after three weeks of culture. This period of time was sufficient for cells to divide and reach good densities, without entering the stationary growth phase. Most of the cells adhere to the bottom of the containers; hence, first of all they have to be detached using a cell scraper. Then, for each strain, all the flasks (30 or 15) or the glass round-bottomed flask were shaken to suspend cells in the water column and the entire culture volume was collected into a 10 L beaker. After homogenization, three aliquots of 4 mL were sampled for cell counting (Multisizer™3 COULTER COUNTER®). Then, the culture was filtered through a 25 µm sieve, and cells were collected into a 50 mL Falcon tube, using sterile seawater. Wet cell pellet was then collected by centrifugation (20°C, 10 min, 3000 g) and stored at -20°C, until extraction.

Figure 19. Example of the harvesting scheme for *G. excentricus* VGO 791 cells (Pisapia et al., 2016).

3.3. Cell counting: MultisizerTM3 COULTER COUNTER[®]

MultisizerTM3 COULTER COUNTER[®] (MSTM3) is used to measure every kind of particles that can be suspended in an electrolyte solution. An electric field is applied and a current path is provided by the electrolyte: the impedance between the electrodes is then measured. The opening of the tube creates what is called a *detection zone*. As a particle passes through the orifice, an electrolyte volume equivalent to the volume of the immersed particle is moved from the *detection zone*. This causes a short-term change in the resistance through the tube aperture. This variation in resistance can be measured or in terms of voltage pulse, otherwise in terms of current pulse (*Multisizer 3 Operator's Manual*).

Figure 20. The Multisizer™3 COULTER COUNTER® system (Multisizer 3 Operator's Manual).

By measuring the number of pulses and their amplitudes, it is possible to obtain information on, respectively, the number of particles and the volume of each particle. This information is then translated by MS™3 software in a graph that expresses the number of particles present in the sample as a function of their size (estimated spherical diameter, ESD).

Figure 21. Diagrammatic illustration of the Coulter Principle applied in the Multisizer™3 COULTER COUNTER® (Multisizer 3 Operator's Manual).

For *Gambierdiscus* cell counting, an aliquot of the culture (4 mL) is diluted with 16 mL filtered seawater (1 to 5 dilution) in 20 mL cuvettes cups. Three counting are made for each sample and results are overlaid by the MS™3 software. After selection of the peak of interest (generally comprised within a range of 40-90 μm diameter) mean cell

concentration and mean diameter, with their corresponding relative standard deviation, are obtained.

Figure 22. Example of a *Gambierdiscus* cell counting.

Mean estimated spherical volume (ESV) is then calculated using the following formula:

$$ESV = (4/3) * 3.14 * (ESD/2)^3.$$

3.4. Toxin extraction and liquid-liquid partitioning

After the cells had been harvested in log phase growth, they were extracted three times with MeOH (1 mL per 3 g wet pellet) using a 3 mm diameter probe sonicator (Q-Sonica, Q700, Newtown, Connecticut USA) at 30% of the total power (500 W). The sonication was conducted in an ice bath (0°C) for 15 minutes in pulse mode (10 s ON, 5 s OFF). At the end

of each sonication step, the supernatant (crude extract) was collected by centrifugation (4°C, 10 min, 4000 g) in a 50 mL Falcon tube. An aliquot corresponding to 1/100 of crude extract volume was stored at -20°C until LC-MS analysis. Crude extract was evaporated under N₂ at 40°C and stored at -20°C. The entire procedure was also done for a solution of pure methanol (blank sample).

Before testing the microalgae extracts on the neuro-2a assay, a prior step of purification was necessary to separate lipophilic CTXs from amphiphilic MTXs. Hence, crude extract residue was suspended in dichloromethane (50 mL per 1 million cells) and partitioned twice in a separatory funnel with MeOH:H₂O (3:2, v/v) (25 mL per 1 million cells) as previously described by (Boyd et al., 2013). The lipophilic CTXs were partitioned into the dichloromethane soluble fraction (DSF) while the amphiphilic MTXs were partitioned into the aqueous methanol soluble fraction (MSF).

Figure 23. Extraction and liquid-liquid partitioning scheme (Pisapia et al., 2016).

Once the DSF and MSF fractions were separated, they were blown dry under N₂ gas at 40°C and stored at -20°C. The residues were re-dissolved in 1.5 mL MeOH or 1.5 mL MeOH: H₂O (1:1, v/v) for the DCM and aq. MeOH fractions, respectively, and filtered on a 0.2 µm sieve. An aliquot of 0.1 mL was stored at -20°C for LC-MS analysis, an aliquot of 0.7

mL was loaded on the Sephadex™ LH-20 column and the remaining 0.7 mL were stored at -20°C.

3.5. Size-exclusion chromatography

The efficacy of size-exclusion chromatography (Sephadex™ LH-20) as a purification step for MTXs contained in the aq. methanol soluble fraction (MSF) was evaluated.

Sephadex™ LH-20 is supplied as a dry powder and must be swollen before use. A weighted amount of the powder (10 g in our study) was suspended in an excess of the solvent to be used in the separation (MeOH 100% in our study) at room temperature for at least 3 hours. Then, fine particles were removed by decanting and a few amount of solvent was added in order to prepare a media slurry (75% settled medium: 25% solvent). The media slurry was gently poured into an open column (intern diameter: 1 cm) in one continuous motion. The bottom outlet of the column was opened and the packing was done at atmospheric pressure until the media bed reached a constant height. The column was equilibrated with MeOH until the baseline became stable (at least two bed volumes). A small volume of MeOH (~4 mL) was left on the top of the media bed and the column inlet was closed with a cap in order to avoid the break of the resin. Before applying the sample, a LH-20 blank sample was collected: the eluent (MeOH 100%) flowed until the meniscus touched the surface of the media bed, then the bottom outlet of the column was closed. Hence, an aliquot of the MSF sample (0.7 mL, diluted to 1 mL) was added dropwise on the resin. The bottom outlet of the column was opened and collection of the first fraction began while the sample was loading on the column. When the meniscus touched the surface of the media bed, the column walls were rinsed three times with 1 mL MeOH 100% to guarantee the complete loading of the sample. Then, a reservoir was added on the inlet of the column and filled with a sufficient amount of MeOH 100% (3-fold column bed volume, 120 mL). Fractions were collected dropwise by atmospheric pressure; the flow rate was calculated to be 0.4 mL min⁻¹.

An open column with an intern diameter of 1 cm was packed with 10 g of Sephadex™ LH-20 powder swollen in methanol (bed height: 52.7 cm, bed volume: 41.4 mL). The MSF

sample of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 was used for the first trial: 50 fractions, 2.5 mL each, were collected. Fractions were screened for toxicity, using the neuro-2a assay, and the preliminary results were promising.

Figure 24. Example of fractionation on a Sephadex® LH-20 column.

In order to optimize the separation, a new collection scheme was used for the other three strains: the first fraction represented from 0 to 10 mL (almost the approximate void volume of the column); then, the following 45 mL were collected mL by mL in silanized glass vials. Finally, two fractions of 30 mL (fractions 47 and 48) were collected for column rinsing. All the 48 fractions were stored at -20°C before neuro-2a and LC-MS analyses. At the end of the collection, a small volume of MeOH ($\sim 4 \text{ mL}$) was left on the top of the media bed and the column inlet was closed with a cap in order to avoid the break of the resin.

The volume of the mobile phase (buffer) is equal to the void volume, V_0 . The void volume, V_0 is the elution volume of molecules that remain in the buffer because they are larger than the largest pores in the matrix ($\text{MM} > 5000 \text{ Da}$) and therefore pass straight through

the packed bed. In a well-packed column, the void volume is approximately 30% (in this study it is equal to $0.30 * 40 = 12$ mL) of the total physical volume (Sunda and Hardison, 2007). It corresponds to the volume in which will be eluted large molecules. Consequently in the first 10 mL it is possible to find very large molecules that will be eluted (including MM > 6000 Da approximately).

Another type of dead volume is the void volume plus the volume occupied by the mobile phase into the pores of the stationary phase. This is the space in which it is possible to find molecules of molecular weight inferior to 5000 Da, which have no interaction with the stationary phase. This would correspond to the dead volume of conventional stationary phase. It is estimated here to 40 mL (using 10 g of LH20 phase and methanol).

3.6. Neuro-2a (N2a) assay

3.6.1. N2a cell maintenance

The neuroblastoma neuro-2a (n2a) cell line was obtained from the American Type Culture Collection (ATCC, CCL 131). N2a cells were grown and maintained in Eagle's Minimum Essential Medium (EMEM, ATCC® 30-2003) containing 2 mM L-glutamine, and enriched with 1 mM sodium pyruvate, $100 \mu\text{g mL}^{-1}$ streptomycin, $100 \text{ units mL}^{-1}$ penicillin, and 10% fetal bovine serum. Growth conditions were kept at 37°C in a humidified 5% CO_2 atmosphere. To prepare for cytotoxicity analysis, N2a cells were harvested with a trypsin-ethylenediaminetetraacetic acid (trypsin-EDTA) solution and seeded into each well of a 96-well microtiter plate at 30,000 cells per $100 \mu\text{L}$ of growth medium under the same growth conditions as above.

3.6.2. Citotoxicity (MTT) assay

Maitotoxins (MTXs) activate non-selective ion channels, which cause an increase of intracellular calcium and triggers cell death.

The cytotoxicity assay for MTX detection used in this study is based on the mouse neuroblastoma neuro-2a (n2a) cell line. This cell line has frequently been used to detect

voltage-gated sodium channel (VGSC) toxins, such as ciguatoxins and brevetoxins, but studies conducted by Satake (1993) extended its application to MTX compounds as well.

N2a cells were homogeneously distributed on 96-well microplates (30,000 cells per well). After 24 h incubation, n2a cells were exposed to the samples to be screened for toxicity and incubated for 2.5 hours. Some wells were exposed to a serial dilution of MTX standard (Wako Chemicals, Ltd.) ranging from 0.29 to 29,126 pg mL^{-1} (concentration in the well) in order to draw a calibration curve allowing to determine the specific toxicity to each sample expressed in MTX equivalents. Non-treated wells (solvent vehicle) were used as control wells to determine 100% viability.

After 2.5 h incubation, the MTT assay was used to assess cell viability (Wu, 2003). In viable cells the yellow tetrazolium salt MTT (3-(4, 5-dimethylthiazol-2-yl)-2, 5-diphenyl tetrazolium bromide) is reduced to an insoluble, purple, formazan product by cytoplasmatic and mitochondrial enzymes such as succinate dehydrogenase (Caillaud et al., 2010b). Dimethylsulfoxide (DMSO) was added to dissolve the formazan product, yielding a colored solution that can be quantified by measuring the absorbance at 544 nm using a Tecan Infinite® M200 plate reader (Tecan, Austria, GmbH). The instrument was set in a *multiple reads per well* mode with 5 flashes.

Figure 25. Interface of Tecan Infinite® M200 plate reader (Tecan, Austria, GmbH) software showing the method for MTT assay.

3.6.3. High content screening (HCS) assay

The high content screening (HCS) assay was performed at *Contaminant Toxicology Unit, ANSES* laboratory (Fougères, France) for *G. excentricus* VGO 791 fractions.

High content screening (HCS) is a recent advance in the automation of quantitative epifluorescence microscopy and image analysis, and in the application of microfluorescent, multiprobe technology. The system is equipped with an incubator that maintains constant temperature, CO₂ and humidity during the analysis. The instrument is able to monitor fluorescence intensity at four wavelengths and at the same time it analyses images and data (Mosmann, 1983).

For n2a cell needs, incubator temperature was set at 37°C with 5% CO₂. N2a cells were homogeneously distributed on 96-well microplates (10,000 cells per well). After 24h incubation, n2a cells were exposed to two fluorescent dyes: Hoechst 33342 (3 μg mL⁻¹) to determine nuclear area and cell number and Fluo-4-AM (5 μM) for intracellular calcium.

Subsequently, cells were exposed to a serial dilution of MTX standard (Wako Chemicals, Ltd.) ranging from 7.8 to 30,000 pM, and to *G. excentricus* VGO 791 samples (MSF and LH-20 fractions). Fluo-4-AM fluorescence was measured at 488 nm using an ArrayScan VTI HCS Reader (Thermo Scientific, Waltham, MA, USA) for 3 min exposure and expressed as a fold of intensity compared to vehicle control condition.

3.7. Liquid Chromatography – High Resolution Mass Spectrometry (LC-HRMS)

Liquid Chromatography-Mass Spectrometry (LC-MS) is a technique which combines high performance liquid chromatography (HPLC), a powerful analytical separation technique, with mass spectrometry (MS), a powerful analysis and detection technique.

3.7.1. LC method

The column used was a Kinetex C₁₈ (50 x 2.1 mm, 2.6 µm) and it was maintained at 40°C. The following mobile phases were used: A) H₂O and B) CH₃CN:H₂O (95:5, v/v), both supplemented with formic acid (HCOOH 50 mM) and ammonium formiate (NH₄⁺ HCOO⁻ 2 mM). The flow rate was set at 0.4 mL min⁻¹ and the chromatographic run lasted 16 min per analysis. Separation was achieved using the following mobile phase gradient: from 10% to 95% B in 10 min, plateau at 95% B for 2 min, return to the initial condition (10% B) in 0.1 min and a re-equilibration period (10% B) for 3.9 minutes (fig. XYZ).

Time [min]	A [%]	B [%]	Flow [mL/min]
0.00	90.00	10.00	0.400
10.00	5.00	95.00	0.400
12.00	5.00	95.00	0.400
12.10	90.00	10.00	0.400
16.00	90.00	10.00	0.400

Figure 26. Gradient used in LC-HRMS analysis for MTX detection.

The sample rack was maintained at 4°C and the injection volume was set at 3 µL.

3.7.2. HRMS analysis

The mass spectrometer used was a Q-ToF 6550 iFunnel (Agilent). The ionization used was electrospray (ESI).

Data were acquired in full scan mode and the instrument operated in negative ion acquisition.

Figure 27. Q-ToF 6550 iFunnel (Agilent) for MTX detection.

Data-mining via LC-HRMS was carried out to manage data complexity and to correlate MS data to cytotoxicity. Raw data were retreated using MassHunter Qual software (v B.07) using an abundance cut-off of 500 counts. MassHunter algorithms recognize isotope clusters and simple derivatives such as water losses. Compound identification was carried out using an in-house developed database. The identification algorithm uses both exact mass and isotope abundance of clusters for assignment to a molecular formula.

CHAPTER FOUR

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

4.1. Maximum growth rates

4.1.1. Results

Gambierdiscus cells were kept in the exponential growth phase using semi-continuous batch cultures (see section 3.1). Maximum growth rates (μ_{\max} , d⁻¹) were calculated using slopes of the linear correlation obtained plotting the natural log of cell biovolume concentration ($L_{\text{cells}} L_{\text{culture}}^{-1}$) against day of culture (Figure 28).

Table 6. Maximum specific growth rates (μ_{\max} , division day⁻¹) with R² of the *Gambierdiscus* strains cultivated in this study.

Species / Strain	μ_{\max} (division day ⁻¹)	R ²	T _d (day)	n	days _{tot}
<i>G. excentricus</i> / VGO 791	0.100	0.992	10.1	13	68
<i>G. excentricus</i> / VGO 792	0.044	0.883	22.9	13	49
<i>G. scabrosus</i> / KW070922_1	0.141	0.995	7.1	15	78
<i>G. sp.</i> / Vietnam	0.121	0.991	8.1	15	78

Figure 28. Linear correlation obtained plotting the natural log of cell biovolume concentration ($L_{\text{cells}} L_{\text{culture}}^{-1}$) against day of culture for the four strains cultivated in this study. Maximum growth rates (μ_{max} , d^{-1}) correspond to the slopes of the linear correlation obtained. A) *G. excrucians* VGO 791; B) *G. excrucians* VGO 792; C) *G. sp. Vietnam*; D) *G. excrucians* VGO 792;

Maximum growth rates (μ_{\max} , division day⁻¹) of *Gambierdiscus* in small-scale culture (horizontal 75 cm² flasks) ranged from 0.044 to 0.141, depending on the strain. Thus, the doubling time (T_d) was comprised between 7.1 and 22.9 days. The slowest growing strain was *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (0.044 division day⁻¹), the fastest one was *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 (0.141 division day⁻¹).

4.1.2. Discussion

Dinoflagellates of the benthic genus *Gambierdiscus* are known to be slow-growing microorganisms, dividing approximately once every three days (Berridge and Tan, 1993). Previous studies are consistent with maximum growth rates generally lower than 0.5 division day⁻¹ (Lehane and Lewis, 2000; O'Brien et al., 2006). In the present study, maximum growth rates (μ_{\max}) were < 0.2 division day⁻¹ for all the four strains cultured.

Kibler et al. (2012) modeled response surface contours for temperature and salinity of the growth rates of four strains belonging to four different *Gambierdiscus* species (Xu et al., 2016). According to the predictive model, *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 cultured at 25°C with a salinity of 33 psu (and an irradiance of 90-100 $\mu\text{mol photons m}^{-2} \text{s}^{-1}$) should be at sub-semi-optimal growth conditions and reach a μ_{\max} within a range of 0.30-0.32 division day⁻¹. In our study the strain grew approximately two times more slowly than expected. We hypothesize that slight differences may exist in μ_{\max} , possibly related to the choice of the culture medium: the IMK/2 culture medium (Yoshimatsu et al., 2014) appeared suitable for growth of Japanese phylotypes as discussed by Yoshimatsu et al. (2014).

For the other strains a comparison between the results of our study and the literature is difficult, because of the difference in estimating cell density methods that exist among studies (e.g. direct-counting under an optical microscope, indirect-counting using an automated particle counter, extracted chlorophyll *a* or *in vivo* chl *a* fluorescence measurements). Also the utilization of different pieces of culturing equipment (size of flasks, materials) and the different combination of culture parameters (source of seawater, nutrients of the medium, salinity, temperature, irradiance, day/night cycle) could be considered as a difference causing item. Also intraspecific variability, should be

considered when comparing clones within the same species, especially if they have genetic differences, so generalizations to sub-species, species or genus levels should be avoided, especially when working with few strains (Yamaguchi et al., 2012; Yoshimatsu et al., 2014).

4.2. Large-scale cultures of *Gambierdiscus* spp.

4.2.1. Results

G. scabrosus KW070922_1 and *G. sp.* Vietnam have higher growth rates (0.141 and 0.121, respectively), for this reason they were the best candidate for a big volume culture test. As shown in Table 7 and Table 8, from April 2016 these two strains were cultivated only in big glass round-bottomed flasks and three flasks.

Table 7. Cell harvesting for *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1.

<i>G. scabrosus</i> / KW070922_1						
Date	Wet pellet weight (g)	Culture volume (mL)	Cell density (cell mL ⁻¹)	Cells harvested	ESD (µm cell ⁻¹)	Container
23/03/2016	0.489	1'350	958	1'293'705	56.9	225 cm ² flasks (x 5)
18/04/2016	7.724	9'200	7'472	68'742'400	46.5	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
12/05/2016	3.608	4'800	2'900	13'920'000	55.1	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
02/06/2016	9.209	4'465	8'737	39'010'705	50.6	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
30/06/2016	6.955	4'900	8'738	42'816'200	52.3	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
27/07/2016	7.339	6'500	8'222	53'443'000	56.4	10 L glass round-bottomed flask + 225 cm ² flasks (x 3)

Initially, 10 L cultures were tested, because, according to (Burkholder and Glibert, 2006), they are more efficient than the 20 L ones. *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 rapidly adapted to the 10 L glass round-bottomed flask, with a significant increase of cell density (from 958 to

7472 cell mL⁻¹) and a decrease in cell size (the mean spherical diameter, ESD, decreased from 56.9 to 46.5 μm). For the following generation, the culture volume was decreased to 5 L: an increase in cell size was observed, but the cell concentration reached was lower. With the following generations, it is possible to observe the adaptation of the strain to the culture conditions: cells had the same diameter they had at the beginning of the study and the cell concentration was significantly increased.

Table 8. Cell harvesting for *G. sp.* Vietnam.

<i>G. sp.</i> / Vietnam						
Date	Wet pellet weight (g)	Culture volume (mL)	Cell density (cell mL ⁻¹)	Cells harvested	ESD (μm cell ⁻¹)	Container
24/03/2016	1.917	2'700	1'993	5'381'100	51.7	225 cm ² flasks (x 9)
18/04/2016	14.251	9'320	8'268	77'057'760	51.6	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
13/05/2016	5.506	5'350	7'122	38'102'700	50.5	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
03/06/2016	5.037	5'150	4'403	22'675'450	52	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
29/06/2016	8.507	5'050	9'398	47'459'900	49.7	10 L glass round-bottomed flask
27/07/2016	7.423	6'900	5'970	41'193'000	51.6	10 L glass round-bottomed flask + 225 cm ² flasks (x 3)

The behavior of *G. sp.* Vietnam is quite different from *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1. The strain seemed to grow well both in 225 cm² flasks and in 10 L glass round-bottomed flasks. The results (Table 8) showed a constancy in cell size (ESD = 49.7-51.7 μm), however, the values of cell number per mL in 10 L glass round-bottomed flask cultures oscillated in a range comprised between 4400 and 9400 cells mL⁻¹ among generations, and it does not seem related neither with the cell size or with the culture volume.

Table 9. Cell harvesting for *G. excentricus* VGO 792.

<i>G. excentricus</i> / VGO 792						
Date	Wet pellet weight (g)	Culture volume (mL)	Cell density (cell mL ⁻¹)	Cells harvested	ESD (µm cell ⁻¹)	Container
22/04/2016	0.719	2'500	262	654'250	74.8	225 cm ² flasks (x 8)
11/05/2016	0.787	4'820	173	835'306	78	225 cm ² flasks (x 14)
03/06/2016	0.524	2'500	137	341'750	82.5	4 L glass round-bottomed flask
03/06/2016	1.44	2'900	518	1'503'070	83.3	225 cm ² flasks (x 10)
30/06/2016	2.945	3'500	1257	43'99'500	72.7	225 cm ² flasks (x 12)
30/06/2016	0.615	2'500	198	495'750	70.2	4 L glass round-bottomed flask
26/07/2016	2.215	3'910	650	2'541'500	74.1	225 cm ² flasks (x 13)
26/07/2016	0.739	2'000	335	670'000	74.3	4 L glass round-bottomed flask
26/07/2016	1.591	4'100	395	1'619'500	72.1	10 L glass round-bottomed flask

The primary results concerning *G. excentricus* VGO 792 cultures were not satisfying, both in 225 cm² flasks and in 4 L glass round-bottomed flasks. As a consequence, throughout generations, higher volumes of inoculum were used in order to increase the possibility that the culture could develop. This technique gave the expected results: cell density increased from 262 cell mL⁻¹ to 1257 cell mL⁻¹ in 225 cm² flasks and from 137 cell mL⁻¹ to 335 cell mL⁻¹ in the 4 L glass round-bottomed flask. The first trial with 10 L round-bottomed flask gave promising results: slightly higher cell density (from 335 to 395 cell mL⁻¹) and slightly lower diameter (from 74.3 to 72.1 µm). Adaptation of this strain to large-scale cultures seems to be slow but first results are promising.

Table 10. Cell harvesting for *G. excentricus* VGO 791

<i>G. excentricus</i> / VGO 791						
Date	Wet pellet weight (g)	Culture volume (mL)	Cell density (cell mL ⁻¹)	Cells harvested	ESD (µm cell ⁻¹)	Container
20/04/2016	0.966	2'710	78	210'025	78.3	225 cm ² flasks (x 9)
11/05/2016	0.588	5'970	29	171'637	78.7	225 cm ² flasks (x 20)
02/06/2016	0.459	5'000	20	100'000	75.4	225 cm ² flasks (x 17)
29/06/2016	0.294	2'750	5	13'750	79.4	225 cm ² flasks (x 9)
29/06/2016	0.269	2'500	5	12'500	70.3	4 L glass round-bottomed flask

Results in Table 10 showed that *G. excentricus* VGO 791 did not adapt to large-scale flasks or glass round-bottomed flask, since the beginning of the study. The procedure was the same as the one used for *G. excentricus* VGO 792, but it did not react in the same way: cell concentration decreased continuously throughout generations.

4.2.2. Discussion

All the strains were cultured under the same experimental conditions. Large-scale cultures were established in order to have sufficient biomass for purification of toxic compounds. *G. sp.* Vietnam and *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 rapidly adapted to large-scale containers, both to 225 cm² flasks and to 10 L glass round-bottomed flasks, reaching maximal cell densities in 10 L glass round-bottomed flasks of, respectively, 9398 and 8738 cells mL⁻¹. Cell harvesting for further extraction and toxin purification was satisfying throughout generations (wet pellet weight ~5-8 g each). *G. excentricus* VGO 792 demonstrated to slowly adapt to large-scale containers, reaching higher cell density when cultivated in 225 cm² flasks (max: 1257 cell mL⁻¹). The first trials with the glass round-bottomed flask system gave promising results, but still not satisfying in terms of cell density (335 cell mL⁻¹ in 4L

glass round-bottomed flask, 395 cell mL^{-1} in 10 L glass round-bottomed flask). Cell harvesting of the following generations will probably give better yields, as the strain seems to need time to adapt to the glass round-bottomed flask system. *G. excentricus* VGO 791, which grew faster than *G. excentricus* VGO 792 in small-scale cultures (see section 4.1.1), did not succeed in adapting to large-scale containers in our study conditions.

4.3. Neuro-2a cytotoxicity (MTT) assay

In this study the capacity of MTXs to induce toxic effects on neuro-2a cells was verified using a standard solution of MTX, and further applied for the screening of the production of MTX-like compounds in the four strains under analysis.

A duplicate for some fraction of interest was done.

4.3.1. MTX standard

MTX standard produces mortality in neuro-2a cells in a dose-dependent manner (Figure 29).

Figure 28. Sigmoidal dose-response curve (SigmaPlot® 12) of MTX standard on the N2a cytotoxicity (MTT) assay after 2.5 h exposure.

4.3.2. MSF samples

MSF extracts were tested to investigate the interaction between *Gambierdiscus* and Neuro2a cells.

Table 11. Calculation of MSF concentration (cell eq mL⁻¹) in the well (full strength).

Strain	Cell number (MSF)	mL MeOH:H ₂ O (1:1, v/v)	MSF (cell eq mL ⁻¹) (initial concentration)	Well volume (μL)	Sample volume (μL)	MSF (cell eq mL ⁻¹) in the well (full strength)
<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 791	2'178'158	1.5	1'452'106	103	3	42'294
<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 792	2'138'398	1.5	1'425'598	103	3	41'522
<i>G. scabrosus</i> KW070922_1	13'751'882	1.5	9'167'921	103	3	267'027
<i>G. sp.</i> Vietnam	49'872'396	1.5	33'248'264	103	3	968'396

4.3.2.1. First experiment with three concentrations tested

Three dilutions of MSF samples (200, 2000, 20000) were initially tested on the neuro-2a assay cells.

Table 12. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations.

<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 791 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	211	9%
dil 2000	21.1	10%
dil 20000	2.11	10%

Figure 29. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

G. excentricus VGO 791 caused the maximum response (9-10% viability) at all the concentrations tested, even at a concentration of 2 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well.

Table 13. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations.

<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 792 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	208	10%
dil 2000	20.8	10%
dil 20000	2.08	47%

Figure 30. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

G. excentricus VGO 792 exhibited remarkable cytotoxicity, causing the maximum response (90-100% reduction of viability) until a concentration of 21 cells eq mL⁻¹ and 50% reduction of viability at a concentration of 2 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well.

Table 14. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. sp. Vietnam* (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations.

<i>G. sp. Vietnam</i> (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	4842	9%
dil 2000	484.2	9%
dil 20000	48.42	14%

Figure 31. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. sp. Vietnam* (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

In the case of MSF from *G. sp Vietnam*, different dilutions of the sample do not result in different neuro-2a viability percentage, giving the maximum response (9-10% viability). Only the concentration of 48 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well produces a change in term of viability (14% instead of 9%).

Table 15. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations.

<i>G. scabrosus</i> KW070922_1 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	1335	11%
dil 2000	133.5	44%
dil 20000	13.35	62%

Figure 32. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 (MSF sample) tested at three concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability

G. scabrosus KW070922_1 was the less cytotoxic strain. Only at a concentration of 1335 cell mL⁻¹ in the well maximum response (11% viability) was obtained.

4.3.2.2. Second experiment with six concentrations tested

In order to better understand the relationship between the sample concentration and the neuro-2a response, each strain was tested at six concentrations. The results are presented as follows.

Table 16. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations.

<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 791 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	211	8%
dil 2000	21.1	8%
dil 20000	2.11	11%
dil 200000	0.211	71%
dil 2000000	0.0211	109%
dil 20000000	0.00211	107%

Figure 33. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

Table 17. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations.

<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 792 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	208	8%
dil 2000	20.8	8%
dil 20000	2.08	56%
dil 200000	0.208	90%
dil 2000000	0.0208	91%
dil 20000000	0.00208	93%

Figure 34. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

Table 18. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. sp. Vietnam* (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations.

<i>G. sp. Vietnam</i> (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 200	4842	8%
dil 2000	484.2	9%
dil 20000	48.42	62%
dil 200000	4.842	100%
dil 2000000	0.4842	100%
dil 20000000	0.04842	95%

Figure 35. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. sp. Vietnam* (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

Table 19. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations.

<i>G. scabrosus</i> KW070922_1 (MSF sample)		
Sample dilution	<i>Gambierdiscus</i> concentration (cell eq mL ⁻¹ in the well)	Neuro-2a cell viability (%)
dil 20	13351	9%
dil 200	1335.1	14%
dil 2000	133.51	64%
dil 20000	13.351	95%
dil 200000	1.3351	102%
dil 2000000	0.13351	101%

Figure 36. Neuro-2a cell viability (%) after 2h30 exposure with *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 (MSF sample) tested at six concentrations. In blue, the bar represents the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* (cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well); in orange, the line represents neuro-2a cell viability.

4.3.2.3. Discussion

In order to compare the cytotoxicity of the four *Gambierdiscus* strains, dose-response curves were obtained plotting neuro-2a cell viability (%) as a function of log₁₀ (cell eq mL⁻¹). These are preliminary results: at least a triplicate should be done for each point of the curve in order to calculate EC₅₀ values.

Figure 37. Dose-response curves for the four *Gambierdiscus* strains. Y axis represents neuro-2a cell viability, X axis represents *Gambierdiscus* concentration (cell eq mL⁻¹) expressed in \log_{10} scale.

G. excentricus VGO 791 was the most cytotoxic strain, presenting high toxicity also at extremely low concentrations: its EC₅₀ is comprised within a range of 1-10 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well. *G. excentricus* VGO 792 was less toxic than VGO 791, with an EC₅₀ comprised within a range of 10-100 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well. *G. sp.* Vietnam showed an EC₅₀ comprised within a range of 100-1000 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well and *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 was the less toxic strain of this study (EC₅₀: 1000-1000 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well). Next step will be to test a triplicate of the samples and convert N2a viability data in pg MTX eq cell⁻¹.

4.3.3. LH-20 fractions

An aliquot of MSF was loaded on LH-20 column and eluted with MeOH according to the collection schemes described above (see section 3.5). It is worth to notice that for *G. excentricus* VGO 791 collection scheme consisted in 50 fractions of 2.5 mL each, while for the other three strains, the first 10 mL were collected in fraction 1 (non-toxic fractions, column dead volume), then 1 mL was collected in the following 45 fractions and 30 mL in fraction 47 and 48 (non-toxic fractions, column rinse).

Table 20. Calculation of cell concentration (cell eq mL⁻¹) in fractions #02→#46.

Strain	SUBSAMPLE of MSF loaded on LH-20 column (mL)	SUBSAMPLE of MSF loaded on LH-20 column (cell number)	Fractions #02--->#46 (mL collected)	Fractions #02--->#46 (cell eq mL ⁻¹)	Well total volume (μL)	Sample volume (μL)	Fraction #02 ---> #46 (cell eq mL ⁻¹) in the well (full strength)
<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 791	0.745	1'081'819	2.5	432'727	103	3	12'604
<i>G. excentricus</i> VGO 792	0.700	997'919	1	997'919	103	3	29'066
<i>G. scabrosus</i> KW070922_1	0.700	6'417'545	1	6'417'545	103	3	186'919
<i>G. sp. Vietnam</i>	0.700	23'273'785	1	23'273'785	103	3	677'877

4.3.3.1. Results

LH-20 fractions were tested on the neuro-2a assay in order to evaluate the efficacy of the size-exclusion chromatography approach in toxic compound recovery. Fractions corresponding to an elution volume > 35 mL are omitted (no toxicity observed).

***G. excentricus* VGO 791**

(MSF LH-20 samples at 6.3 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well)

***G. excentricus* VGO 792**

(MSF LH-20 samples at 14.5 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well)

G. sp. Vietnam

(MSF LH-20 samples at 338.9 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well)

Figure 38. Results of the neuro-2a assay concerning LH-20 fractions of four *Gambierdiscus* strains (MSF samples). Neuro-2a cell viability (%) is expressed as a function of the fraction number and its corresponding LH-20 elution volume.

LH-20 fractions of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF sample) showed, at a concentration of 6.3 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well, MTX-activity only from #06 to #09 (elution volume = 12.5-22.5 mL), with the most toxic fraction being fraction #07 (elution volume: 15-17.5 mL). Similarly, *G. excentricus* VGO 792 (MSF sample) showed, at a concentration of 14.5 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well, MTX-activity from #06 to #10 (elution volume: 14-19 mL), with the most toxic fraction being fraction #07 (elution volume: 15-16 mL). *G. sp.* Vietnam showed, at a concentration of 338.9 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well, MTX-activity from #07 to #14 (elution volume: 15-23 mL), with the most toxic fraction being fraction #08 (elution volume: 16-17 mL). *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 showed, at a concentration of 934.6 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well, MTX-activity from fraction #05 to #10 (elution volume: 13-19 mL), with the most toxic fraction being fraction #07 (elution volume: 15-16 mL).

4.3.3.2. Discussion

MSF fractionation showed that toxic compounds elute early (from 14 to 23 mL), right after the dead volume of the LH-20 column. This evidence suggests that *Gambierdiscus* strains present in this study probably produce high molecular weight MTX analogs. The next step will be to test a triplicate of the samples and convert N2a viability data in pg MTX eq cell⁻¹.

4.4. Neuro-2a high content screening (HCS) assay

4.4.1. Results

Fluo-4-AM fluorescence was used to measure intracellular calcium in neuro-2a cells (section 3.6.3). Results were expressed as a fold of intensity compared to vehicle control condition.

Figure 39. Sigmoidal dose-response curve (GraphPad Prism 6.0) of MTX standard on the N2a HCS assay after 3 min exposure.

In Figure 40 it is possible to observe an increase of intracellular calcium due to MTX standard (Wako Chemicals, Ltd.), in dose-dependent manner.

Figure 40. Fluo-4-AM fluorescence intensity after 3 minutes exposure with *G. excentricus* VGO 791.

Crude extract and MSF of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 increased Ca^{2+} levels in neuro-2a cells, indicating that the toxic compounds exhibit a similar effect on N2a cells as that of MTX. LH-20 fractions of MSF from #06 to #10 ($V_{\text{MeOH}} = 12.5\text{-}25$ mL) showed an increase in intracellular calcium levels as well, between 1.5 and 1.8 fold to control (Figure 41).

4.4.2. Discussion

The neuro-2a high content screening (HCS) assay allowed to correlate neuro-2a cell death caused by *G. excentricus* VGO 791 (MSF and LH-20 fractions) with Ca^{2+} -related activity. Both cytotoxicity and changes in intracellular calcium coincided well in early eluting fractions (from #06 to #10, 12.5-25 mL): the early elution of toxic components suggests

high molecular weight and Ca^{2+} -increase points towards maitotoxin mechanism of action. These results strongly suggest that *G. excentricus* VGO 791 produces MTX analogs.

It would be interesting to test LH-20 fractions of the other strains for comparison purpose.

4.5. LC-HRMS

4.5.1. Results

Crude extract, MSF and toxic LH-20 fractions of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 were analysed via LC-HRMS techniques (full scan mode, negative ion acquisition). No known MTX was found in any of the extracts: this fact suggests the existence of a (or more than one) hitherto unknown compound responsible for the activity in cellular assay.

Figure 41. MS spectra (negative ion acquisition) obtained in full scan mode. -EIC of MTX standard ($[M-2H]^{-2}$ at m/z 1688.7968, RT = 5.823 min). -ECC of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 samples: crude extract, MSF, LH-20 fraction #07.

The crude extract of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 contained 1312 compounds. After liquid-liquid partitioning, the aqueous methanol soluble fraction (MSF) contained 725 compounds. Thus, the liquid-liquid partitioning resulted approximately in a purification of a factor 1.8. The LH-20 fractions of MSF which exhibited strong activity on the neuro-2a assay, *i.e.* from fraction 6 to fraction 10 ($V_{elution}=12.5-25$ mL), contained between 25 and 51 compounds. In particular, fraction 7, the most toxic one, contained only 40 compounds, which represents approximately 1/33 of the initial compound number.

4.5.2. Discussion

Preliminary results for *G. excentricus* VGO 791 strain showed that LH-20 reduced data complexity, from more than one thousand compounds in the crude extract to only 40

compounds in the most toxic LH-20 fraction. Thus, fractionation via size-exclusion chromatography (LH-20) seems to be a suitable strategy for *Gambierdiscus* toxin purification. In particular, LH-20 is an efficient clean-up step for high molecular weight compounds as it allows for a purification to a stage where individual compounds may be evaluated as candidates. Furthermore, high resolution mass spectrometry permits evaluation of compounds for similarity with known MTXs. Further studies will focus on identification of hitherto undescribed toxic compound(s).

CHAPTER FIVE

CONCLUSIONS AND PERSPECTIVES

One of the objectives of this work was to establish large-scale laboratory cultures of four different *Gambierdiscus* strains for toxin purification. Results suggest that *Gambierdiscus* does not easily adapt, in a short period of time, to large-scale horizontal flasks or to glass round-bottomed flasks with gentle air bubbling. *G. sp. Vietnam* and *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 demonstrated the capability to adapt well to large-scale containers and reached high cell densities at the chosen conditions of temperature, salinity and nutrients. Initial trials on *G. excentricus* VGO 792 showed that the strain could slowly adapt to large-scale containers but cell densities were low. *G. excentricus* VGO 791 did not grow well in large-scale cultures. In the latter case, a change in culture medium or salinity condition could be helpful. Lots of information about the nature of those organisms and their growth conditions can be gleaned from studies on growth rates, and, for this reasons, combined tests of different culture media could be an interesting development. Another improvement could be achieved with horizontal plastic bags because it increases the air exchange and the surface/volume ratio.

Neuro-2a cytotoxicity (MTT) assay has allowed comparison of cytotoxicity among the four *Gambierdiscus* strains. Preliminary studies carried out on a serial dilution of the MSF samples permitted to establish the relationship between the concentration of *Gambierdiscus* cell equivalents tested and the toxicity observed. *G. excentricus* VGO 791 was the most toxic strain, presenting high toxicity also at extremely low concentrations (EC_{50} comprised within a range of 1-10 cell eq mL^{-1} in the well). However, the issue persists in the development of this strain in large-scale laboratory cultures. *G. excentricus* VGO 792 was less toxic than VGO 791, with an EC_{50} comprised within a range of 10-100 cell eq mL^{-1} in the well. Nevertheless, this strain was able to adapt to large-scale cultures, so it will be

useful to continue cultivating this strain for toxin isolation purpose. *G. sp.* Vietnam showed that EC₅₀ was comprised within a range of 100-1000 cell eq mL⁻¹ in the well, while *G. scabrosus* KW070922_1 was the least toxic strain (1000-10000 cell eq mL⁻¹).

Neuro-2a cytotoxicity (MTT) bio-assay also has identified the cytotoxic and non-cytotoxic fractions after size-exclusion chromatography. The detection of cytotoxicity in the early eluting fractions is consistent with high molecular weight compounds such as MTX analogs. Next step will be to test a triplicate of the fractions of interest and convert N2a viability data in pg MTX eq cell⁻¹ (ongoing).

Neuro-2a high content screening (HCS) assay has been useful to correlate neuro-2a cell death caused by toxic fractions of *G. excentricus* VGO 791 with an increase of intracellular Ca²⁺. Both cytotoxicity and changes in intracellular calcium coincided well in early eluting fractions (from #06 to #10, 12.5-25 mL): the early elution of toxic components suggests high molecular weight and Ca²⁺-increase points towards maitotoxin mechanism of action.

LC-HRMS (Q-ToF 6550) techniques have evaluated the efficacy of sample preparation for MTX detection, from cell harvesting to toxin extraction and purification (liquid-liquid partitioning and size-exclusion chromatography). MS spectra (negative ion acquisition) showed that the purification procedure considerably reduced data complexity (from ~1300 compounds in the crude extract to 40 compounds in the most toxic fraction of *G. excentricus* VGO 791). This part of the work is still ongoing, with the aim of pinpointing to individual candidates as new MTX analogs.

Wood and Leatham (1992) reported the detection of *Gambierdiscus* cells in samples collected from Crete Island in 2007. This record could indirectly indicate the consequences of climate change in this area, suggestion which is in agreement with the discussion about the *tropicalization* of the Mediterranean Sea (Bomber, 1987) and the possibility of geographical expansion of tropical microalgae, such as *Gambierdiscus*, due to climate change (Aligizaki and Nikolaidis, 2008). However, the increasing record of *Gambierdiscus* in more temperate areas such as the Mediterranean Sea might be due to an intensified

research in this field during the last few years, and it is not possible to know if *Gambierdiscus* was already present before or if it has recently expanded to these new areas. Nevertheless, the presence of *Gambierdiscus* suggests that the gradual increase in sea surface water temperature facilitates acclimation and settlement of such tropical species, as it is the case for other marine organisms (Aligizaki, 2009).

The presence of *Gambierdiscus* species in the Mediterranean Sea may imply the onset of ciguatera in this area. This constitutes a serious hazard for human health and sea-related activities and for those reasons further researches on this genus are needed. Comparison of cytotoxicity of different strains and species is useful to evaluate risk assessment. In the case of our study, *G. excentricus* VGO 791 could be newsworthy because it showed high toxicity and its ecophysiological needs in terms of temperature and salinity are close to the ones of the Mediterranean Sea. If the strain reached the Mediterranean Sea, it would be harmful not only for fishery industries, but it could also cause other problems: increase in health-related costs (Aligizaki, 2009), loss of labor productivity (Occhipinti-Ambrogi, 2007), loss of food source (Hajkowicz, 2006), loss of reef-fish sales in local and international markets (Bagnis et al., 1992), loss of tourism (Lewis and Ruff, 1993), and, in some cases, depopulation through migration (Lewis and Holmes, 1993).

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